

HEAT-HEALTH ANALYSIS REPORT 1

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Author(s)	Chloe Brimicombe, Katharina Wieser, Tobias Monthaler, Ilona M. Otto (UGRAZ), Cherie Part, Debra Jackson (LSHTM), Michalis Koureas, Georgios Charvalis, Katerina Kontouli (UTH), Massimo Stafoggia, Federica Nobile (DEP-Lazio), Jeroen De Bont, Nathalie Roos (KI), Aquinius Mung'atia, Zeenat Sulaiman (AKHS Kenya), Matthew Chersich, Lebohang Radebe (Wits RHI), Stanley Luchters (UGent/CeSHHAR)
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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
AKHS	Aga Khan Health Services (Kenya)
ANC	Antenatal care
AT	Apparent Temperature
BMI	Body mass index
CEDAP	Certificate of Delivery Care Registry (Italy)
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CI	Confidence interval
COST	European Cooperation in Science and Technology
ELSTAT	Hellenic Statistical Authority
ERA5	The 5th European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Reanalysis Product
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HDSS	Health and Demographic Surveillance System
HIV/AIDS	Human immunodeficiency virus/acquired immunodeficiency syndrome
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
DEP-Lazio	Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service, ASL Roma 1
KI	Karolinska Institutet (Sweden)
LSHTM	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom)
MNCH	Maternal, Neonatal, and Child Health
MRT	Mean radiant temperature
NoSQL	Not Only Structured Query Language (describes a type of database design)
NUTS-1	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics type 1 for major socioeconomic regions
OR	Odds ratio
RR	Relative risk
SPR	Swedish Pregnancy Register
SQL	Structured Query Language (to create and manage relational databases)
U5MR	Under-five mortality rate
UGent	Ghent University (Belgium)
UGRAZ	University of Graz (Austria)
UK	United Kingdom
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index (a thermal comfort index)
UTH	University of Thessaly (Greece)
VIDA	Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics (University of Witwatersrand)
WBGT	Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (a heat stress index)
Wits RHI	Research institute of the University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa)

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document provides an overview of the environmental and health analysis that has taken place for D2.3. This document builds on the work in D2.1. It provides an overview of data analysis for fifteen countries on a national, sub-national or local level, for common health outcomes of preterm birth and under-five mortality and climate exposure indicators. The aim of the analysis is to evaluate the impact of extreme heat on two health outcomes to investigate and provide insights on key thresholds and trends. In addition, an international perspective on these two health outcomes is offered.

1.2 Relation to other project work

This deliverable influences the direction of the project for the next years. It provides key information across the work packages of WP2, 3 and 4. Some of the notable connections are:

- D2.4 Heat-health analysis report 2 (due August 2025)
- D3.2 Indicators selected (due February 2024)
- D3.3 Report on predictive heat warning thresholds (due January 2024)
- D4.1 Training on use of monitoring indicators (due April 2024).

1.3 Variations to the project proposal

This deliverable is subject to differences from the original HIGH Horizons proposal. These differences include a smaller dataset than anticipated in the East Africa region for only one hospital in Mombasa, Kenya. In addition, robust ethics processes in South Africa resulted in delays with the analysis and also smaller in scope than in other regions. Thanks to extra Horizon Europe funding through the Hop On Facility, the project was able to gain another partner organisation with health data from Greece, thus expanding our analysis. To be flexible and also adapt our research further, the

approach taken was to also evaluate Health and Demographic Surveillance Sites consolidated data for sub-Saharan Africa.

1.4 Structure of the document

This document has six main chapters. First an overview of the background of the impact of heat exposure and maternal, perinatal and child health is outlined in Chapter 2. Then, the types and sources of data used in the document are described in Chapter 3. Next, the methodologies are in Chapter 4. In Chapter 5 the results of the document are highlighted. The discussion and links with the wider body of literature are outlined in Chapter 6, before concluding in Chapter 7.

2 Background

Climate change is causing a rise in extreme heat exposure on a global scale and is a growing risk to every part of the world [1]. It is evident that both Europe and Africa are warming faster than the overall average land temperature and experiencing an increase in intensity, duration, and frequency of the occurrence of extreme weather [1]–[3]. This presents cross-sectoral challenges for societies including challenging infrastructure, increasing demands on health services, and affecting people’s day to day lives [4]. These challenges are not felt uniformly with certain parts of society being more vulnerable [5]. Two groups that are more vulnerable to extreme heat are pregnant women and children. Because of their limited capacity to thermoregulate, i.e., how the body maintains core temperature during increased ambient temperatures, which can present a range of health challenges [6]. For example, pregnancy represents a crucial stage of development that is highly susceptible to the effects of environmental exposures [7]. These exposures can jeopardize the normal growth of the foetus and lead to long-lasting negative consequences for the health of the child, potentially affecting future generations as well [8].

Preterm birth is defined as a baby born alive before 37 weeks of gestation. Preterm birth can further be divided into moderate preterm birth (after 32 and before 37 gestational weeks), very preterm birth (between 28 and before 32 gestational weeks) and extremely preterm birth (less than 28 gestational weeks) [9]. Globally, it accounts for 10% of all births [10]. Despite significant improvements in recent decades, it remains the leading cause of neonatal and under-five child mortality. The causes are multifactorial, and some risk factors have been identified such as maternal infections, maternal age, high body mass index (BMI), previous preterm birth, maternal comorbidities such as diabetes, chronic hypertension, previous surgery for cervical pre-cancerous lesions etc. In addition, stress has been identified as an important risk factor and includes, thermal stress, intimate partner violence and major life events.

Infants who are born preterm are at higher risk of long-term sequelae and life-consequences such as lower educational achievement, behavioural disorders, with increasing risk with lower gestational age. Many survivors of preterm birth face a lifetime of disability, including learning disabilities and visual and hearing problems. In the immediate, these infants require prolonged neonatal care and require monitoring during infancy.

Preterm birth is an adverse health outcome associated with increased ambient temperatures. A systematic review by Chersich et al. from 2020 identified 47 studies demonstrating the harmful direct impacts of heat on preterm birth rates. Association with preterm births in some analyses shows a 1.05-fold increase in the incidence of preterm birth for every 1°C rise in temperature and the odds of experiencing a preterm birth were observed to be 1.16 times (16%) higher during heatwaves (95% confidence interval 1.10 to 1.23; $I^2=44.7%$) [11].

Furthermore, previous research has demonstrated a significant link between leading causes of child mortality and climate change, such as malaria, child wasting and stunted growth, and indications of prolonged chronic undernutrition [12], [13]. For example, one study found that heat related child mortality is projected to double by 2050 under

a high emission scenario for Africa [14]. Another study found that exposure to daily daytime mean temperatures of higher than 35°C was associated with an increased risk of stunted growth in children of 1.27 (CI 1.16–1.38) [15].

An estimated 13.4 million babies were born preterm in 2020. In addition, approximately 900 000 babies died of complications of preterm birth in 2019 [16]. In 2020 the global under-five mortality rate (U5MR) fell to 37 deaths per 1000 live births, but children in sub-Saharan Africa continued to have the highest rates of mortality in the world at 74 deaths per 1000 live births [17]. Climate change presents another challenge to reducing child, infant and perinatal mortality rates and reducing the number of preterm births.

While there is evidence to support pregnant women, infants, and children being vulnerable groups to extreme heat [18]-[19], there is considerable heterogeneity in the analytical methodologies, exposure metrics, and windows of susceptibility examined in the current literature base, which limits synthesis and comparability of findings across studies and contexts.

Research to date has primarily focused on mean air temperature as the environmental exposure of interest. However, mean air temperature does not adequately capture the level of heat stress that a population is exposed to and other environmental exposures (including humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation) should also be taken into account. Heat stress indices are a current methodological approach for improving the accuracy of considering the burden of heat on the body. They include: (i) the *Universal Thermal Climate Index* (UTCI), developed as part of a COST action [20], [21]; (ii) *Wet Bulb Globe Temperature* (WBGT), the current international standard for considering the effects of heat stress on occupational health [22]; and *heat index* which is a type of 'apparent temperature', an empirical approximation of the combined effects of air temperature and relative humidity on a human [23].

This report sums up two independent analyses. First, the findings of data analysis from five countries exploring the effects of mean daily temperature, and where possible heat index, Universal Thermal Climate Index and Wet Bulb Globe Temperature on preterm

births (defined as birth <37 weeks of gestation), including data from Italy, Greece, Sweden, South Africa and Kenya. A homogenous study design is used, and exposure metrics are unified to enable cross-country comparison. We aim to answer: *Is there a difference in the effect of heat exposure on preterm birth using different heat metrics? And is the pattern of response different across different countries and climate zones?*

Second, it sums up findings on the effect of Wet Bulb Globe Temperature on under-five mortality for twelve countries in sub-Saharan Africa with the aim to answer: *What is the impact of heat stress as indicated by the international standard metric of wet bulb globe temperature on neonatal, infant and child mortality rates? And is there a difference for the relationship between heat exposure and the impact on child mortality rates, across seasons?*

3 Data types and sources

3.1 Health data

3.1.1 Italy

The data source is the Certificate of Delivery Care Registry (CEDAP) of Lazio Region (regional database) [24]. The dataset contains all-live births between 2001 and 2019 for a total of 856 700 births from women with a geo-spatial coded residence in the region (approximately 40 000 births per year) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of births in the Lazio Region per year

The dataset contains information on maternal and infant characteristics as well as socioeconomic information (date, hospital of delivery, singleton or twin pregnancy, sex of the infant, gestational age, birth weight, etc.) and about the woman (maternal age, parity, educational level, employment status, origin, geocoded residence, etc.). For our analysis, we included singleton births ($n = 827\,987$), of which 49 584 (6.0%) were born preterm (< 37 gestational weeks). The preterm birth rate (per 1000 live births) was quite consistent in the analysed period and varied between 50 and 70 (Figure 2). No seasonal trend was detected (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Preterm births rate (per 1000 births) in the period 2001-2019 in the Lazio Region

Figure 3: Boxplot assessing seasonal trend of percentage of preterm births (%)

3.1.2 Greece

The national dataset from Greece includes 2 316 655 births between 1999 to 2021. Available variables for each birth include i) live or stillbirth, ii) cause of stillbirth, iii) person present at birth, iv) gestational age at birth, v) birth weight (grams), vi) maternal age, vii) mode of delivery (vaginal birth, caesarean section, instrumental delivery), viii) maternal nationality, ix) marital status, x) residence (urban/rural/semi urban), and xi) number of newborns. The date of birth (DD/MM/YY) and the municipality of residence of the mother is available for all births. Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT) is the owner of the data. Nationwide data on hospitalizations of pregnant women from 1999-2015 are also used. The dataset contains geographically aggregated data on hospitalisation per ICD code falling into the “Pregnancy, childbirth and the puerperium” category (1999-2012: ICD-9, 2014-2015: ICD-10). Similarly, data on hospitalizations of children up to 1 year of age have been acquired. For the purpose of the present report only birth data are presented. Table 1 presents the frequencies of categorical variables, and the means (Standard Deviation) and medians (min, max) of quantitative variables.

Table 1: Summary statistics of key variables recorded at birth (Nation-wide data 1999-2021)

Variable	N (%)
Preterm birth: <i>Delivery of a live born infant at less than 37 weeks' gestation</i>	
No	2 095 469 (90.5%)
Yes	211 366 (9.1%)
Missing	9 820 (0.4%)
Moderately preterm: <i>Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 32 and < 37 weeks' gestation</i>	
No	2 120 119 (91.5%)
Yes	186 716 (8.1%)
Missing	9 820 (0.4%)
Very preterm: <i>Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 28 and < 32 weeks' gestation</i>	
No	2 288 836 (98.8%)
Yes	17 999 (0.8%)
Missing	9 820 (0.4%)
Extremely preterm: <i>Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 22 and < 28 weeks' gestation</i>	
No	2 300 258 (99.3%)
Yes	6 577 (0.3%)
Missing	9 820 (0.4%)

Variable	N (%)
Low birth weight: <i>Delivery of a live born infant weighing less than 2500 grams</i>	
No	2 107 024 (91.0%)
Yes	197 311 (8.5%)
Missing	12 320 (0.5%)
Moderately low birth weight: <i>Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 1500 to < 2500 grams</i>	
No	2 130 829 (92.0%)
Yes	173 506 (7.5%)
Missing	12 320 (0.5%)
Very low birth weight: <i>Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 1000 to < 1500 grams</i>	
No	2 288 012 (98.8%)
Yes	16 323 (0.7%)
Missing	12 320 (0.5%)
Extremely low birth weight: <i>Delivery of a live born infant weighing < 1000 grams</i>	
No	2 296 853 (99.1%)
Yes	7 482 (0.3%)
Missing	12 320 (0.5%)
Stillbirth	
No	2 306 540 (99.6%)
Yes	10 115 (0.4%)
NUTS1 region of residence	
EL3	847 016 (36.6%)
EL4	274 565 (11.9%)
EL5	644 762 (27.8%)
EL6	543 896 (23.5%)
Missing	6 416 (0.3%)
Maternal age at birth	
Mean (SD)	30.4 (5.61)
Median [Min, Max]	31.0 [11.0, 64.0]
Residence	
Urban	1 596 262 (68.9%)
Rural	346 827 (15.0%)
Semi- Urban	367 150 (15.8%)
Abroad	6 300 (0.3%)
Unknown	116 (0.0%)

For our analysis concerning live preterm births, a total of 211 366 were recorded during the period covered, corresponding to an overall 9.12% (95% confidence intervals (CI): 9.09%-9.16%) preterm birth proportion. Temporal and geographical variations of

preterm birth rate (preterm/total births) are observed. Figure 4 presents the geographical distribution of preterm birth rates at commune level in Greece from 1999 to 2021. In Figure 5, the proportion of preterm births by month of delivery is displayed as a percentage with corresponding 95% CI. Elevated rates are evident in May, June, July, and December, whereas March and April exhibit lower values.

Figure 4: Preterm Birth Rates (%) across Greek municipalities (communes)

Figure 5: Temporal (monthly) distribution of preterm birth rates in Greece

3.1.3 Sweden

The data used come from the National population based Swedish Pregnancy Register, which covers 92% of all births in Sweden and registers approximately 100 000 births per year. The current register for the analyses encompasses the period starting 1st January 2014 until 31st December 2018. The Pregnancy Register collects data on pregnancy and childbirth, starting at the first visit to antenatal care and ending at the follow-up visit to the antenatal care, which usually occurs at around 8–16 weeks postpartum. The majority of data is collected directly from electronic medical records. The Register includes demographic, reproductive and maternal health data, as well information on prenatal diagnostics, and pregnancy outcome for the mother and the newborn and is used for research on pregnancy and early childhood as well as for quality improvement [25]-[26]. Each individual in Sweden has a unique personal identifier [27] assigned at birth or immigration and is used to link the pregnant women in the Swedish Pregnancy Register with the National Patient Register (for maternal and neonatal health outcomes, both in- and out-patient care) and Statistics Sweden for socioeconomic information and residential address information. From a total of 560 615 singleton live births, 28 221 (5.1%) were born preterm. Those born moderately preterm (32-36 gestational weeks) were 25 691 (4.2 %), very preterm (28-31 gestational weeks) 2 914 (0.5%) and extremely preterm (less than 28 gestational weeks) 2 095 (0.4%) (Figure 6).

In addition, the Swedish Pregnancy Register can differ between spontaneous and medically indicated preterm birth. During the period 2014-2018 there were 25 304 (4.2%) spontaneous preterm births and 5 396 (0.9%) medically indicated preterm births (Figure 7). The summer months in Sweden, when the temperatures on average are the hottest, are June, July and August. The trend of preterm birth in Sweden increases during the fall with a peak in November with 5.9% in preterm birth rate (Figure 8).

Figure 6: Bar chart depicting preterm birth rates by gestational age category in the Swedish Pregnancy Register 2014-2018

Figure 7: Spontaneous and medically indicated preterm birth in the Swedish Pregnancy register 2014-2018

Figure 8: Trend preterm birth (less than 37 gestational weeks) in the Swedish Pregnancy Register 2014-2018

3.1.4 South Africa

The data used are a regional/sub-national database from the Soweto District. The Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics (VIDA) Research Unit of the University of the Witwatersrand, led by Professor Shabir Madhi, funds and maintains a passive surveillance (birth register) dataset for the Soweto region of South Africa.

Information is recorded on all deliveries at midwife-led clinics and tertiary referral hospital in the region (N = 10), including date of admission, date and time of delivery, maternal characteristics (age, parity, gravidity, nationality), morbidities (e.g. maternal HIV status) and complications at birth, number of infants born, mode of delivery (vaginal delivery, caesarean section), assisted delivery (vacuum extraction, forceps), caesarean section (emergency, elective), reason for caesarean section, duration of delivery (HH:MM), gestational age at birth (completed gestational weeks), birth outcome (live born, fresh stillbirth, macerated stillbirth), infant characteristics (sex, birth weight, head circumference, length), APGAR score at 5 minutes and 10 minutes of life, and condition of the child (transferred to mother, transferred to nursery, died, other). The database includes approximately 220 000 births between April 2016 and March 2022. It is estimated that this dataset includes 98% of births that occurred in Soweto during this period (Statistics South Africa, 2020).

Following the advice of the data owners, cases of preterm birth were identified from deliveries recorded in the tertiary referral hospital only. This was due to the higher quality gestational age information at this facility.

3.1.5 Kenya

The data used are from 2017 to 2022 for Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa. This is a local scale dataset. Data are retrieved using the Aga Khan Hospital Surveillance Dashboard. On average, there are about 650 births in the hospital each year. Data records include but are not limited to information on type of delivery, stillbirths, APGAR scores and live preterm births.

Figure 9 seems to indicate that most preterm births may take place in January (median = 5) at the beginning of the hottest period, and again towards the end of a short rainy season (April/May) in Kenya. However, small numbers of deliveries limits our ability to interpret the data.

Figure 9: Boxplot of the seasonal trend of number of preterm births

Note: Red indicates the hottest season, blue indicates monsoon/rainy season and cream indicates dry season.

3.1.6 Sub-Saharan Africa

The data and analyses come from the INDEPTH network and the Health and Demographic Surveillance System (HDSS). These are consolidated data from 29 sites from across sub-Saharan Africa from 12 countries of The Gambia, Senegal, Ghana, Burkina Faso, Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Ethiopia, Tanzania, Uganda, Malawi, Mozambique and South Africa [28]. The data were collected through surveys taking place every month, from 1990 until 2019. The data scale ranges from sub-national to a single settlement.

The focus of the analysis in this study is on the all-cause mortality of children aged over 1 year and under 5 years), infants (under 1 year) and neonates (under 28 days). These groups are defined using the recorded date of birth in comparison to the date of death. It should be noted, as in prior research, it is found that records are subjective to 'data heaping' on the 15th day of the month [29]. Given the presence of data heaping the

data are pooled on a monthly temporal scale into 6 different climate regions based on literature on the migration of monsoons and temperature trends (West Monsoon 1,2,3, East Monsoon, South Africa and Ethiopia) [30]–[33].

Figure 10 shows the seasonal trend of the neonatal, infant and child mortality rates. For all regions we can see a clear seasonal trend, allowing us to hypothesize that causes of mortality may be linked to seasonal patterns such as rainfall and temperature distribution. For Ethiopia, West Monsoon 3 and the East Monsoon, we can see that the highest mortality rate is occurring when the temperature is at some of its highest values in May, October and January respectively. The highest mortality rates in South Africa are seen in April, which can be considered a transition period, this is where swings in temperature and the diurnal range of temperature are greater than at other times of the year. For West Monsoon 1 and 2 the highest mortality rates are within the monsoon season.

3.2 Climate data

Heat exposure is assessed using heat metrics, alongside ambient air temperature. Heat metrics to be evaluated alongside temperature were chosen based on a previous study by Ioannou et al., (2022) which showed that across physiological studies Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) and the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) outperformed other indices across a range of physiological tests such as heart rate and metabolic rate [34]. In addition, a scoping review of heat metrics used in perinatal and maternal health studies was carried out and showed that alongside WBGT and UTCI, heat index and apparent temperature have previously been used by studies [35]. The difference between these heat metrics are the inputted meteorological data considered and their heat transfer models, the methodology is outlined below.

Figure 10: Showing the seasonal pattern of pooled data from 1990 until 2019 for neonatal, infant and child mortality rates across different climate regions in Africa

Note: Months 1, 2, ... 12 correspond to January, February... till December. Blue bar = Rainy Season; orange bar = Hot Season

We make use of a state-of-the-art dataset ERA5, that provides global gridded data every 1 hour at a 0.25x0.25° grid scale [36]. This provides data for regions where observations are sparse, including sub-Saharan Africa. We use the raw output data to create several heat metrics and then explore the impact of either high perceived temperatures or temperature on health outcomes [37]. These data are aggregated into daily mean, maximum and minimum values.

❖ **Universal Thermal Climate Index**

The Universal Thermal Climate Index is a bioclimatological model of an average human body's response to different thermal conditions where the subject is not acclimatised to the climate and is outdoors, doing minimal work i.e., walking at about 3.5km/hr [20]. It was developed in the early 2000s as part of the COST Action 370 "Toward a universal thermal climate index UTCI for assessing the thermal environment of the human being". The Universal Thermal Climate Index is different to other heat metrics in the inclusion of the body model known as the Fiala Model [20]. Another key difference of this index is that it is optimized across cold and hot conditions and can be used as a measure of the likelihood of cold or heat stress occurring [38].

To counter the inaccessibility to run the Fiala model on computers in the early 2000s, a 6-order polynomial approximation and look-up tables were created. Most research continues to use a 6-order polynomial in the absence of access to the Fiala model [21]. The input variables that are used to create the UTCI are air temperature (K), dew point temperature (K), mean radiant temperature (K) and wind speed (m/s). The data for the UTCI are available as part of the ERA5-HEAT dataset [38].

❖ **Wet Bulb Globe Temperature**

Wet Bulb Globe Temperature is an international standard for heat stress in occupational settings [39]. Wet bulb globe temperature was created in the late 50s to put in place protections for the US military against the hot environment [40].

Wet bulb globe temperature is calculated using observations from a wet bulb thermometer – a thermometer wrapped in a damp muslin cloth, a globe thermometer to measure incidence of radiation and a dry air thermometer – or approximated using empirical models of these values. Here, we use outdoor or effective Wet Bulb Globe Temperature [40].

The equation to calculate wet bulb globe temperature is:

$$WBGT = 0.7T_w + 0.2T_g + 0.1T_d$$

Where t_d is dry bulb air temperature, t_g is globe temperature and t_w is wet bulb temperature.

❖ Heat Index

Heat index is a type of apparent temperature adapted from an original Steadman method [23], which takes into account the combined effects of air temperature and relative humidity. Originally the method was not compatible with global climate zones, having a limited range for high humid and high temperature values, and this was therefore extended using a polynomial approximation into a method used by the National Weather Service in the US as part of their heat early warning system which can be seen in this equation:

$$HI = -42.379 + 2.04901523 T + 10.14333127 R - 0.22475541 TR - 0.00683783 T^2 - 0.05481717 R^2 + 0.00122874 T^2 * R + 0.00085282 T * R - 0.00000199 T^2 * R^2 + ADJ$$

Where, $ADJ=0$ unless (1) $R > 85\%$ and T is between 80 and $87^\circ F$, then $ADJ = [(R-85)/10] * [(87-T)/5]$

T is air temperature ($^\circ F$) and R is Relative Humidity (%)

Our calculations of heat metrics were carried out on an hourly temporal scale for a global grid using the *thermofeel* python library developed by the European Centre for Medium Range weather forecasts [37]. This is an extension of the earlier ERA5-HEAT dataset [38].

❖ Downscaling pilot of climate data in Greece

Health data in the Greek dataset are aggregated at the municipality (commune) level, making the ERA5-Land dataset a more suitable choice for analysis compared to ERA5

0.25°x 0.25° grid. The direct solar radiation at the surface level (fdir) is not available in ERA5-Land but is necessary to calculate mean radiant temperature (MRT) and other heat metrics. To address this issue, we employed a methodology to calculate this, and subsequently all heat indicators for the ERA5-Land 0.1° x 0.1° grid. Finally, we generated time series data for each Greek commune for the specified period. Additional details on this methodology can be found in appendix C.

3.3 Geolocating climate and health data

The climate and health data are on different scales, and this requires us to use geolocation and statistical downscaling. We have two types of health data, point data with longitudes and latitudes and sub-national regions. In both cases the approach taken is to interpolate using a weighted nearest neighbour approach and the schematic in Figure 11 visualizes the method [41], [42]. Once the climate data are ‘matched’ to the health data this allows for the climate and health data to be merged and the relationship evaluated.

Figure 11: A schematic explaining the statistical downscale approach of the climate data to the scale of the health data to allow for comparisons between climate and health data

4 Methodology

4.1 Time-series regression

A time-series is “a sequence of data points recorded at regular time intervals” (typically, daily) [43]. Time-series regression is used to assess if/how time and event/outcome are related. The unit of analysis is day, and the outcome is a daily count of adverse health events (cases) [43]. Therefore, data are fully anonymized and individual-level data are not required. The aim is to examine short-term associations between exposure and outcome (e.g. are month-to-month fluctuations in the number of preterm births explained, in part, by changes in temperature). Here, a polynomial model is fitted to the dataset and where appropriate lags up to 3 months prior investigated. Outcomes are displayed as risk ratios at the 95th percentile vs the heat metric value of the 50th percentile.

4.2 Time-stratified case-crossover design

This design offers a complementary method to time-series analysis and has been widely used to study short-term effects of environmental exposures on risk of adverse health outcomes [44], including preterm birth [45], [46]. A person’s exposure levels on the day of the health event (“case day”) are compared with that same person’s exposure levels on otherwise similar days (“control days”) [47], [48]. Cases serve as their own controls, which removes the possibility of control-selection bias [49] and inherently adjusts for individual-level confounders that are fixed (or vary slowly) over time, e.g., maternal age, education, ethnicity, socio-economic status. In this methodology, controls are typically defined as the same day of the week within the same month and year as the case day (providing 3-4 controls per case); thereby also adjusting for season, time-trend, and day-of-week by design [48]. Outcomes are displayed as odds ratios at the 95th percentile vs the heat metric value of the 50th percentile, for up to a period of 7-day lags.

In summary, while we tried for consistent analyses across sites, some variation did exist due to differences in sample size or data sources, as outlined in table 2. The study

protocol for this report is in appendix A and examples of all the analysis scripts used in this report are included in appendix B.

Table 2: Summary methods by site of analyses

Site	Source: Exposures	Source: Outcome(s)	Analysis Methods	Measures of Effect
Lazio Italy	ERA5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air temperature WBGT UTCI 	Regional Health Data: Preterm	Time Stratified Case-Crossover with 0-6 day lag	1) OR (95% CI) for 95 th vs 50 th Percentile 2) Dose-response/ Association Curves
Greece	ERA5-Land: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air temperature WBGT UTCI Heat Index 	National Health Data: Preterm	Time Stratified Case-Crossover with 0-6 day lag	1) OR (95% CI) for 95 th vs 50 th Percentile 2) Dose-response/ Association Curves
Sweden	ERA5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air temperature WBGT UTCI 	National Health Data: Preterm	Time Stratified Case-Crossover with 0-6 day lag	1) OR (95% CI) for 95 th vs 50 th Percentile 2) Dose-response/ Association Curves
South Africa	ERA5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Daily Mean air temperature 	Soweto regional Tertiary Hospital Data: Preterm	Time Stratified Case-Crossover with 0-6 day lag and lag stratified by day	1) OR (95% CI) for 95 th vs 50 th Percentile 2) Dose-response/ Association Curves
Kenya	ERA5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air Temperature WBGT UTCI 	AKU Hospital Data: Preterm	Time Series Regression with no lag, prior 1 month lag and prior 3-month lag	1) RR (95% CI) for 95 th vs 50 th Percentile 2) Dose-response/ Association Curves
Sub-Saharan Africa (6 regions) West 1,2,3 East Africa Ethiopia South Africa	ERA5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> WBGT 	HDSS Data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Child Mortality Infant Mortality Newborn Mortality 	Time Series Regression with no lag, for whole year and for hottest period	1) RR (95% CI) for 95 th vs 50 th Percentile 2) Dose-response/ Association Curves

5 Results

5.1 Italy

The Lazio Region dataset included 827 987 singleton births between 2001 and 2019. Of these, 49 584 (6.0%) were born preterm. We analysed three different heat metrics (air temperature, wet bulb globe temperature and universal thermal climate index) and preterm birth through a time-stratified case-crossover design.

When comparing the 95th vs the 50th percentile of the heat metrics, we estimated an odds ratio (OR) OR = 1.121 (95% CI, 1.033; 1.217), OR = 1.118 (95% CI, 1.030; 1.214) and, OR = 1.118 (95% CI, 1.031; 1.212), using air temperature values, WBGT and UTCI, respectively (Table 3).

Table 3: Associations between short-term exposure (lag0-6) to high levels of different heat metrics, and preterm births (comparing 95th vs 50th)

Indicator	95th percentile of heat metric (Celsius)	50th percentile of heat metric (Celsius)	OR (95% CI) (95th vs 50th)
Air temperature	25.49	15.63	1.121 (1.033-1.217)
Universal Thermal Climate Index	27.30	14.90	1.118 (1.031-1.212)
Wet Bulb Globe Temperature	23.16	14.00	1.118 (1.030-1.214)

The shape of the relationship between the heat metrics and preterm births was mostly linear, above all between the 50th and the 90th percentile; it is supralinear in the case of WBGT (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Association between air temperature during the week preceding births and the risk of preterm births using different heat metrics

Note: a) air temperature, b) wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT) and c) universal thermal climate index (UTCI) (the lines represent the 1st, 50th, 75th, 90th, 95th and 99th percentile).

5.2 Greece

The selection of the optimal model parameters was based on the analysis of the relationship between air temperature and preterm births. In particular, we extracted lagged (0-6 days) temperature data from a dataset, and subsequently constructed a series of cross-basis objects within the `dlnm` R package. Each employed a distinct functional form to represent the temperature-preterm birth relationship. These included polynomial functions, B-splines, and natural splines with varying degrees of freedom and lag terms. Furthermore, we computed and utilized key percentiles and quantiles of the temperature data to inform the selection of appropriate knots in natural spline models. Conditional logistic regression models were then fitted for each cross-basis object. To evaluate the models, we calculated AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) values, enabling us to make informed model selections. The model of the lowest AIC value was selected as the best fitting for all subsequent analysis.

Figure 13 presents the effect of air temperature on the risk of preterm birth for all models, where similar association patterns are observed. The selected model uses B-splines with 5 degrees of freedom for the exposure dimension and a second-degree polynomial for the lagged dimension.

Figure 13: Effect of air temperature on Preterm Birth by 26 model modifications

When comparing the 95th percentile exposure to the 50th percentile exposure for each heat metric, significant associations were observed (Figure 14). The odds ratios ranged from 1.083 to 1.091 (see table 4), indicating an increased risk of preterm birth when exposed to higher levels of these heat metrics. All indicators showed a very similar effect.

Figure 14: Exposure response associations between selected heat metrics and preterm birth

Note: A) mean temperature, b) universal thermal climate index (UTCI) c) wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT) and d) heat index. Dashed lines represent the 95th and 99th percentiles for each heat metric.

Table 4: Associations between short-term exposure (lag0-6) to high levels of different heat metrics, and shortening pregnancy (comparing 95th vs 50th)

Indicator	95 th percentile (Celsius)	50 th percentile (Celsius)	OR (95% CI) (95 th vs 50 th)
Heat Index	27.85	16.30	1.086 (1.047-1.127)
Air temperature	27.92	16.64	1.083 (1.044-1.125)
Universal Thermal Climate Index	28.89	16.14	1.086 (1.048-1.126)
Wet Bulb Globe Temperature	27.33	18.64	1.091 (1.051-1.132)

5.3 Sweden

The Swedish population included 560 615 singleton births between 2014 and 2019. Of these, 28 221 (5.1%) were born preterm. In Sweden, we observed statistically significant associations between short-term exposure to each heat metric and preterm births. In particular, when comparing the 95th vs the 50th percentile, we estimated an OR = 1.11 (95% CI, 1.01; 1.23) using air temperature values (Table 5). We further observed an OR = 1.10 (95% CI, 1.00; 1.23) and OR = 1.10; (95% CI, 1.00; 1.23) using wet bulb globe temperature and universal thermal climate index, respectively.

Table 5: Associations between short-term exposure (lag0-6) to high levels of different heat metrics, and shortening pregnancy (comparing 95th vs 50th)

Indicator	95 th percentile (Celsius)	50 th percentile (Celsius)	OR (95% CI) (95 th vs 50 th)
2 metre temperature	19.9	7.5	1.11 (1.01, 1.23)
Universal Thermal Climate Index	18.7	11.1	1.09 (0.99, 1.19)
Wet Bulb Globe Temperature	16.8	12.5	1.10 (1.00, 1.22)

The shape of the relationship between the heat metrics and preterm births was mostly linear and almost identical in each of the heat metric (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Association between air temperature during the week preceding births and the risk of preterm births using different heat metrics

Note: a) air temperature, b) wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT) and c) universal thermal climate index (UTCI)

5.4 South Africa

We identified 18 272 cases of preterm birth (< 37 weeks' gestation; 19.3%) from 94 663 live singleton births at one tertiary referral hospital in the Soweto District between 01 April 2016 and 31 March 2022. Of those preterm births, 13 848 (75.8%) were moderately preterm (≥ 32 to < 37 weeks' gestation), 3 083 (16.9%) were very preterm (≥ 28 to < 32 weeks' gestation), and 1275 (7.0%) were extremely preterm (≥ 22 to < 28 weeks' gestation).

Risk of preterm birth increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) as temperatures rose above 20.5°C (Figure 16). As shown in Figure 17, the association was strongest at 0-1 day lag. A similar pattern was observed for all subcategories of preterm birth (Figure 18).

Figure 16: Association between daily mean 2m air temperature and odds of preterm birth 0-6 days before delivery

Note: X indicates temperature of minimum effect (20.5°C). Blue dashed line indicates 5th percentile of daily mean temperature (9°C) and red dashed line indicates the 95th percentile (22.5°C)

Figure 17: Effect of exposure to 22.5°C vs 20.5°C on each individual lag day

Figure 18: Cumulative effect of exposure to 22.5°C vs 20.5°C over 0-6 day lag period, by subcategory of preterm birth

5.5 Kenya

The relative risk is not significant for the monthly mean of the daily mean temperature, the monthly mean of the daily mean wet bulb globe temperature of the monthly mean of the daily mean universal thermal climate index (Figure 19). The significance could be affected by the small sample size, and this is widely documented in demographic studies [50]. The central value is set as the median value of heat exposure. For three of the heat exposure metrics, UTCI, WBGT and mean temperature, the relative risk is higher for values above the median in comparison to this value, suggesting that heat exposure is influencing the number of preterm births. In addition, higher values of relative risk are seen in the lag for 3 months prior to the preterm birth count. The small sample size means that the time series regression method is used for results here. A case-crossover design would not be an appropriate methodological choice due to small sample size. This is also why results are explained differently to other countries.

Figure 19: Showing the dose-response curves for relative risk of the monthly mean of daily mean wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT)

Note: A, B, C the monthly mean of Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT); D, E, F the monthly mean of daily mean temperature; and G, H, I the monthly mean of the daily mean Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) at no lag, 1 month prior and 3 months prior.

5.6 Preterm birth cross-country summary

The results from the cross-country studies show that there is a comparable response curve for raised risk of incidence of preterm birth with heat exposure across all countries included in the case-crossover design. One notable response curve is for WBGT and preterm birth in Italy, that is different from the other metrics evaluated. In addition, we see that there is little difference for the chosen methodology between the odds ratio for different heat metrics (Figure 20). The main difference between countries is the absolute value of the threshold at which the indication of heat exposure starts to influence a rise in risk for preterm birth, which differs depending on the existing climate of each country. However, the odds ratios have a very small difference of 0.2 between countries for the 95th percentile compared to the 50th percentile, demonstrating the international risk of heat for odd of preterm birth.

Figure 20: The odds ratio for preterm birth for the 95th percentile vs the 50th percentile across different countries for different heat metrics

5.7 Sub-Saharan Africa

Over the period of the HDSS data from January 1993 until December 2016, there are a total of 44 909 deaths in children under five, with 10 078 neonatal, 14 141 infant and 20 690 child deaths recorded. The average child mortality rate for the HDSS sites is 5.65 (deaths per 1000 live births), the average infant mortality rate is 3.30 and the average neonatal mortality rate is 2.3 per 1000 live births. The pooled descriptive statistics by climate region can be seen in Table 6.

Considering the relative risk ratios at the 95th percentile in comparison to the median (50th percentile) shows that on average there is a smaller confidence interval for the whole year in comparison to the hottest season (Figure 21). In addition, we can see a difference in the effect of heat on child, infant and neonatal mortality rates, evident from changes in the relative risk ratios. For example, for Ethiopia the relative risk ratio is 0.79 (0.73, 0.87) for children, 0.99 (0.9, 1.07) for infants and 1.14 (1.06, 1.23) for neonates. For East Africa the relative risk ratio is 1.27 (1.19, 1.36) for children, 1.06 (1.00, 1.17) for infants and 1.02 (0.96, 1.08) for neonates. For South Africa the relative risk ratio

is 0.94 (0.84, 1.06) for children, 0.97 (0.86, 1.10) for infants and 0.97 (0.84, 1.10) for neonates. For West 1 the relative risk ratio is 0.90 (0.81, 1.01) for children, 0.94 (0.83, 1.07) for infants and 1.04 (0.94, 1.15) for neonates. For West 2 the relative risk ratio is 0.92 (0.88, 0.97) for children, 0.94 (0.89, 0.99) for infants and 0.98 (0.92, 1.03) for neonates. Finally, for West 3 the relative risk ratio is 1.11 (1.04, 1.18) for children, 1.03 (0.97, 1.09) for infants and 1.00 (0.95, 1.06) for neonates.

Across the whole year a significant rise in relative risk of a higher mortality rate for children is only present for East Africa and West Monsoon 3 (Figure 22, Part 1, C, F). However, when considering the hottest season we see a significant rise in relative risk for South Africa, East Africa, and West Monsoon 1 (Figure 22, Part 2, A, C, D). These results show that response of the relative risk of a higher mortality rate in comparison to WBGT values can change based on the season and time evaluated.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics for pooled HDSS sites across climate regions and seasons for Average Child, Infant and Neonatal Mortality Rate and Average Daily Maximum Wet Bulb Globe Temperature

Region	Season	Average Child Mortality Rate	Average Infant Mortality Rate	Average Neonatal Mortality Rate	Average Daily Maximum Wet Bulb Globe Temperature
		Deaths per 1000 live births	Deaths per 1000 live births	Deaths per 1000 live births	°C
West 1 (Burkina Faso, Northern Ghana)	All	3.5	2.1	1.6	28.3
	Dry	3.1	1.9	1.6	28.2
	Monsoon	4	2.4	1.6	27.5
West 2 (South Ghana, Ivory Coast, Nigeria)	All	5.5	3.4	1.9	27.3
	Dry	5.5	3.4	1.9	25.6
	Monsoon	5.5	3.5	1.9	29
West 3 (Senegal and The Gambia)	All	9.2	4.9	3.7	27.6
	Dry	8.5	4.6	3.5	26.7
	Monsoon	10.3	5.3	4.1	29.1
East (Kenya, Malawi, Tanzania, Mozambique, Uganda)	All	7.7	3.5	2.4	23.5
	Dry and Hot	4.6	4	2.4	24.9
	Monsoon 1	4.6	3.7	2.5	24.1
	Dry and Cold	4.2	3.4	2.4	22
	Monsoon 2	6.8	3.1	2.5	24.5
Ethiopia	All	3.9	2.7	2.9	21.3
	Dry	3.7	2.6	3	21.3
	Wet	4.2	4.6	2.9	21.1
South Africa	All	4.1	3	1.3	22.5
	Summer	2.4	2.7	1.2	25.4
	Autumn	4.5	3	1.3	19.2
	Spring	2.5	2.6	1.4	22.5
	Winter	5	2.9	1.3	23.2

Figure 21: The mortality rates relative risk ratios for the 95th percentile in comparison to the median heat exposure for South Africa, East Africa, West 1,2,3 and Ethiopia

Note: Child Mortality Rate relative risk ratio whole year a) and b) hottest season; Infant Mortality Rate relative risk ratio whole year c) and d) hottest season; and Neonatal Mortality Rate relative risk ratio whole year e) and f) hottest season

Figure 22: The relative risk response curve of child mortality rate in comparison to WBGT values, where the median is the centroid

Note: 1) is for the response over the whole year and 2) is for the season where the monthly average of the daily maximum WBGT is at its highest value. A, South Africa, B, Ethiopia, C, East Africa, D, West Monsoon 1, E, West Monsoon 2, and F, West Monsoon 3.

6 Discussion

6.1 Interpretations

❖ Different heat metrics for measuring effect of heat exposure on preterm birth

To our knowledge, this is the first cross-country study that makes use of the heat metrics of wet bulb globe temperature and universal thermal climate index as measures of heat exposure on the response of risk of preterm birth. In addition, only one study uses heat index across all seasons as a measure of heat exposure for a preterm birth outcome [51].

Our results only show a small negligible difference between the analysed heat metrics (daily mean temperature, WBGT, UTCI, Heat Index) and incidence of preterm birth. This differs from a cross-country study on different heat metrics and all-cause mortality across all age groups. However, the biologic pathways for preterm birth and heat related mortality are different and we use a slightly different methodology [52], [53]. Recent discussions on the use of heat metrics for epidemiological studies, that traditional studies using only temperature are thought to not capture the influence of humidity on health outcomes [54].

Most studies in the perinatal and maternal health field continue to use mean temperature and given the comparable response of heat metrics within epidemiological studies this is understandable [11], [55], [56]. However, within physiological studies consistently heat metrics are shown to be a better indication of the body-heat balance [34], [57]. In addition, for the thermal environment the combination of humidity and high temperatures is a more deadly combination than conditions of low humidity and high temperatures, and this is because high humid conditions limit the ability to dissipate heat through sweating and the skins surface [58]. There has also been an uptake in the use of heat metrics in the climate field in recent years at odds with the wider health and epidemiological fields [38], [57].

We suggest a two-fold approach is needed: 1) an increase in the number of studies using heat metrics for a range of health outcomes and 2) further investigations on the influence of humidity on biological pathways and health outcomes.

❖ **Preterm birth risk - differences across different countries and climate zones**

Our results show that there is no difference in overall risk of preterm birth and heat exposure across countries. Where the difference is evident is the threshold at which heat exposure causes a raised risk of preterm birth. In comparing the seasonal distribution plots we see a reduction of preterm birth in both Greece and Sweden in months of highest temperatures, but which also correspond to traditional holiday periods. Communications with clinical colleagues confirm that holidays appear to influence preterm birth numbers positively due to lower stress levels in spite of higher temperatures.

In the case of the heat index, UHCI and WBGT, each metric comes with universal thresholds that are supposedly indicative of likelihood of raised risk of heat stress [21], [59], [60]. This is at odds with our findings, in most cases the value of minimum response is lower than the minimum heat threshold in the metrics. Within the climate field, studies have started to assess the difference between common thresholds for heatwaves such as the 90th percentile and the 95th percentile of a certain region in a certain season over a 30 year-period and the universal thresholds [32], [61]. A comparable type of study design is also evident in many epidemiological studies, where many types of heat exposure are often taken into account [46], [62]. With this in mind, we suggest that the universal thresholds are not continued to be used and are adapted where possible for key differences that effect thermoregulation (i.e., age, sex, pre-existing medical conditions, acclimatization, whether someone is used to their surrounding climate).

Preterm birth is a multifactorial health outcome, meaning it has a complex mix of factors that can lead to the outcome occurring, i.e. in some cases the risk of an illness

for mother or baby can lead to an early induction causing a preterm birth [18], [56]. In addition, we know from other studies on the influence of heat exposure on preterm birth that socio-economic factors, as well as medical factors have an important role in raising someone's vulnerability to heat [5], [63], [64]. Given the source of the data and the case-crossover design used here it was not possible to explore the influence of socio-economic factors for this cross-country study, but we hypothesize that this could influence the value where exposure to heat raises the risk of a preterm birth outcome but is unlikely to alter the response curve.

❖ **Impact of heat stress (using WBGT) on neonatal, infant and child mortality rates**

There is a difference in the relative risk response curve for the African climate regions and seasons to heat exposure. In addition, there is a difference between child, infant and neonatal mortality rate responses to heat exposures. This can in part be explained by differences in the leading cause of death that make up the greatest proportion of all-cause mortality [65]–[67]. For example, for child mortality rates where the leading cause is malaria, it is more likely that exposure to abnormal heat is apparent in the annual relative risk [68]. In addition, where the leading cause of mortality is malaria or HIV amongst children there is a significant positive relationship [66], [67] between exposure to abnormal heat for the hot or/and dry season in comparison to where the leading cause is pneumonia or malnutrition [65]. The leading cause of death for most sites is different for children and infants compared to neonates.

The leading cause of death across different age groups is vital and, in some cases, it was not clear from literature what the leading cause of death for different age categories was. In comparison, it was not always clear whether heat influenced a leading cause of death, for example birth asphyxia [69]. Whilst for other causes such as preterm birth, stunted growth and malaria, the association is better documented [11], [15]. We therefore suggest that future studies look in more detail at specific leading causes of mortality with gaps and the association with extreme heat. For example,

although there is a lack of evidence for the association between birth asphyxia and heat, it can be theorized that heat stress which can influence production of cortisol could influence the biological pathways causing a reduction in oxygen to the foetus [69].

To assess the impact of heat exposure on mortality rates we used an international standard metric of the wet bulb globe temperature [39]. Very few studies have used this metric for studies on children under the age of 5 [70]. The primary use of WBGT is in occupational settings, where universal rest-work guidelines are issued across ages, sex and climate region [39]. Having universal heat metric thresholds is at odds with our results shown here, there are differences in responses to different exposures of heat across ages, seasons and climate regions. It is essential that thresholds are developed that reflect these differences.

❖ **Impact of heat exposure on child mortality rates - differences across seasons**

In most epidemiological studies, there is no consideration of the change in the relative risk response curve over different seasons or amongst different climate zones, with season being added into an overall model as an adjustment [29], [64]. This differs from the existing literature on heat exposure and heatwaves from climate studies. For example, most studies for the African continent use a type of monthly moving average approach as a threshold for indication of extreme heat [32]. Our results demonstrate that whilst useful, pooling health outcomes such as all-cause mortality over multiple seasons and climate zones could be misleading about the nuances in the response to heat exposure. For example, in the case of South Africa there is evidence that the leading cause of death amongst children differs across different seasons [67]. We suggest that more studies consider seasonal differences in response curves. The benefit of this approach is it indicates not only values of importance for associated risk but also times during the year where health professionals and communities can be more aware and give improved guidance.

6.2 Limitations

There are limitations of both the studies in this report, that are important to outline. In the case of the Kenyan and HDSS data analyses it was not possible to carry out a case-crossover design analysis and therefore a time series regression is used, which makes it slightly more challenging to draw conclusions in comparison to the broader cross-country study. In the case of the most extreme heat values above the 95th percentile, there is a broadening of the confidence interval because of a reduction in the sample size being exposed to values in this category. We do not exclude for induced preterm births for medical reasons and this could be adding uncertainty to the results.

6.3 Summary and recommendations

To our knowledge, this is the first cross-country study that makes use of multiple heat metrics as measures of heat exposure on the response of incidence of preterm birth. We find that there is not a difference in overall response for incidence of preterm birth and heat exposure across countries. The difference comes from the value of heat exposure as indicated by the type of heat metric. In addition, we see different results for all-cause mortality in children under the age of five. For example, there is a difference between child, infant and neonatal mortality rate responses to heat exposures, related to leading cause of death and seasonality.

From our two studies we make suggestions for directions of future research:

- an increase in studies using heat metrics for a range of health outcomes;
- further investigations on the influence of humidity on biological pathways and health outcomes;
- more studies including an in-depth look on different seasons and a focus on transition periods as well as the hottest season; and
- thresholds are also evaluated across seasons as well over the whole year.

We hope that our results here will be able to help shape the future of the maternal, child and climate health field.

7 Implications for HIGH Horizons

The results in this report are important for other work within the HIGH Horizons project. We outline here how the analysis has contributed to our understanding and suggestions we would now make based on the results for heat-health indicators and heat-health early warning system development.

7.1 Outcomes for heat-health indicators

The evidence from prior studies, and confirmed by our results here, are that preterm birth would likely be an adverse health outcome which could act as a heat-health indicator, when combined with a heat metric. Preterm birth has a large health burden, being a leading cause of neonatal and infant death in many regions of the world, as well as presenting other health challenges. In our results, we demonstrate an association in all countries and that the response curve for exposure to heat is the same over multiple different countries, and that when comparing the odds risk ratio at the 95th percentile vs the mean that there is a very small difference between countries in terms of risk. We show no difference in response of heat exposure by different metrics, except for one case in Italy for Wet Bulb Globe Temperature. It may, however, be useful to have the same heat metric in an indicator as in an early warning system, as the evidence from both could benefit tracking the impact of climate change and heat on preterm birth more so than if each programme or initiative used a different heat metric.

In addition, we explore all-cause mortality in children under the age of five. Whilst there are multiple previous studies for all-cause mortality and excess deaths during heat, we do not see the same outcome as for preterm birth: response curves differ per-region, per-season and per leading cause of death. All-cause mortality in neonates, infants and young children in each case could be considered a type of composite indicator, given that multiple health conditions lead to the outcome. The benefits are that we can see the effect of heat on a combination of outcomes, but it however has the disadvantage that the attribution of ambient heat is not as easy to discern as with preterm birth.

7.2 Outcomes for heat-health Early Warning System development

Our results for both the preterm birth and all-cause mortality in children under the age of five demonstrate that the universal thresholds for indication of risk of heat stress in heat metrics such as the UTCI and WBGT are not applicable in this context. It is also clear from our results that there is a different threshold for different climate zones, and that sometimes these zones occur within the same country (i.e. Northern Ghana vs Southern Ghana).

The values of the mean do not seem to be a robust suggestion for a warning threshold, being quite low in a lot of cases and may over warn for the hottest periods. For the whole year from the preterm birth study the 75th percentile could represent a robust threshold with the evidence presented, because it does not over warn, but still captures a rise in risk that is not evident in the higher percentile values like the 90th and 95th. We, however, would suggest that a seasonal threshold approach is taken either for periods of 30 days or across climate zones defined seasons, because of the results seen in the all-cause mortality in children under the age of five.

7.3 Future work

The next step is developing several peer-reviewed publications on different aspects of this deliverable. In addition, webinars and blogs can be developed that focus on explaining the implication of this work to key stakeholders and other partners in the HIGH Horizons consortium. We also see this deliverable as a stepping stone to further collaboration between our partners and where appropriate others to expand analyses to other aspects of maternal, perinatal and child health (please see our priority list in Appendix A of the protocol) relevant to numerous aspects of the project going forward. As part of our dissemination approach, we aim to harmonize analysis across datasets and where possible adhere to open science principles by making our analysis scripts available to others where our data is sensitive.

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9 Appendices

9.1 Appendix A: Study protocol

Heat Indicators for Global Health (HIGH Horizons): Monitoring, Early Warning Systems, and health facility interventions for pregnant and postpartum women, infants and young children, and health workers

Protocol:

**HIGH Horizons Population-Level Heat-Health Impacts Study
in Greece, Italy, Kenya, South Africa and Sweden**

Version 7.0 dated 31 July 2023

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Definition
ANC	Antenatal care
AT	Apparent Temperature
EU	European Union
ENS	Early Notification System
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIV/AIDS	Human immunodeficiency virus/acquired immunodeficiency syndrome
MNCH	Maternal, Neonatal, and Child Health
UK	United Kingdom
WBGT	Wet-bulb globe temperature
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work package

Study synopsis

Rationale: The frequency, intensity, and duration of extreme weather events, including heatwaves, have increased in the past four decades and are projected to continue rising. Accumulating epidemiological evidence shows an increased risk of adverse health outcomes for pregnant women, newborns, and young children associated with exposure to extreme heat and high ambient temperatures. There is also some evidence to suggest that heat exposure during gestation has long-term health consequences for the child. This study forms part of the larger HIGH Horizons project, focussed on the impacts of climate change, and specifically heat, on maternal, neonatal and child health (MNCH). The study will inform the selection of heat-related indicators for monitoring and surveillance purposes, development of meaningful heat thresholds, and the design and implementation of a personalised Early Notification/Warning System.

Importantly, the study is designed to understand the relationships between heat exposure and health outcomes during pregnancy, the postpartum and neonatal

periods, as well as early childhood. The study will be conducted in multiple countries, varying in climate zones and socio-economic characteristics, which will increase international representation and generalisability.

Objectives:

Primary:

- 1) To quantify relationships between ambient temperature exposures and risk of adverse maternal, neonatal, and child health outcomes;
- 2) To identify the relative temperature threshold(s) above which risk of an adverse outcome is increased;
- 3) To determine valid and reliable heat indicators for assessing heat-MNCH impacts at population-level;
- 4) To characterise groups of pregnant women and children at high risk of heat-related conditions;
- 5) To determine if heat-MNCH associations vary by location, climate, facility, or quality of care, as the data allow.

Secondary:

- 6) To identify critical windows of susceptibility during gestation or during infancy and childhood;
- 7) To explore impacts of both acute and cumulative heat exposures.

Study design: The study will follow a time-series approach to assess the impacts of high environmental temperature and heat stress on adverse MNCH outcomes. The study is observational (non-interventional), using data from secondary sources only. No primary data will be collected.

Methods: Maternal, perinatal and neonatal health data from different registries and cohorts will be used across different settings and population characteristics. Daily time-series of exposures (such as minimum, mean, and maximum temperatures, universal thermal climate index, wet-bulb globe temperature, apparent temperature,

and relative humidity) have been constructed from hourly openly available reanalysis data, obtained from the Copernicus Climate Data Store or other relevant data repository for each country. Daily exposures will be linked with MNCH outcomes in time and space, including varying lag structures. We will employ a range of complementary analytical approaches, including time-series regression, time-stratified case-crossover, and time-to-event analyses to model associations between environmental exposures and MNCH outcomes.

Ethical considerations: All partners will obtain approval from relevant ethics committees in countries where the data originate and where data analyses will take place. The data will be anonymized, and results will be presented in aggregated format so that individuals will not be identifiable.

Dissemination: Outputs from this study will be presented at different international scientific fora for maternal, neonatal and child health as well as climate change. Scientific evidence generated from the project will be published in scientific peer reviewed articles. Additionally, results will be disseminated among local, provincial and national government officials, advocacy groups, and researchers to support policy changes.

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Study partners and investigators

Study partners:

Name of institution	Country	Address
London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)	United Kingdom	Keppel Street, WC1E 7HT, London
Climate and Health Directorate, Wits RHI, University of the Witwatersrand	South Africa	22 Esselen Street, Hillbrow Health Precinct, Hillbrow, 2001
Centre for Sexual Health & HIV & AIDS Research (CeSHHAR)	Zimbabwe	4 Bath Road, Belgravia, Harare
University of Thessaly	Greece	Argonafton & Filellinon, Volos 382 21
Karolinska Institutet	Sweden	Department of Medicine, Solna, 17177, Stockholm
Aga Khan Health Services Kenya	Kenya	Avenue 3 Rd, 00100, Nairobi
University of Graz (UNI GRAZ)	Austria	Universitätsplatz 3, Graz 8010
Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service, ASL Roma 1	Italy	Via Cristoforo Colombo, 112 - 00147 Roma

The other collaborating partners in the HIGH Horizons consortium are:

- Ghent University (UGENT) – serves as the overall project coordinator.
- Lunds Universitet (ULUND) – offers unique technologies for early warning systems (EWSs) and critical capacity in coding for tailoring the ClimApp to the target audience and optimizing its functionality.
- Denmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU) – The Indoor Environment Section at DTU Sustain has long-term expertise in characterizing exposures from the indoor environment and assessing their effect on people’s comfort, health, and performance, and in the development of sustainable technical solutions for heating, cooling, and ventilation of buildings.
- World Health Organization (WHO) – provides guidance on indicators and surveillance and ensures the project findings are adequately exploited at the EU and global level.

Study investigators

Name of institution	Investigators
London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)	Prof Debra Jackson (Principal Investigator), Prof Veronique Filippi, Dr Cherie Part
Wits RHI, Climate and Health Directorate	Prof Matthew Chersich (Principal Investigator), Dr Gloria Maimela
Centre for Sexual Health & HIV & AIDS Research (CeSHHAR) & Ghent University	Prof Stanley Luchters (Principal Investigator)
University of Thessaly	Prof Hadjichristodoulou Christos (Principal Investigator), Dr Barbara Mouchtouri, Dr Maria Kyritsi, Dr Michalis Koureas, Georgios Charvalis, Dr Georgios Georgakilas, Katerina Kontouli
Karolinska Institutet (KI)	Dr Nathalie Roos (Principal Investigator), Prof Olof Stephansson, Dr Petter Ljungman, Dr Jeroen de Bont Dr Massimo Stafoggia, Dr Federica Nobile (ASL Roma)
University of Graz (UNI GRAZ)	Prof Ilona Otto (Principal Investigator), Dr Chloe Brimicombe

Study rationale

Context

Like all other regions of the world, Europe and Africa have experienced changes in precipitation and temperature over the past four decades as a result of anthropogenic climate change. Temperatures are rising (Gebrechorkos et al., 2019, Almazroui et al., 2020, Fitzpatrick et al., 2020, IPCC, 2021), and extreme heat events are increasing in frequency and intensity (Ceccherini et al., 2017). It is estimated that 48-74% of the global population will be exposed to more than 20 days of deadly heat per year by 2100 (Mora et al., 2017). Africa has been shown to be particularly vulnerable to climate change and extreme heat events because of poverty, poor sanitation, high prevalence of malnutrition, infections, non-communicable diseases, poor quality housing and weak, non-resilient health care systems.

A series of systematic reviews by members of the HIGH Horizons team identified in excess of 200 studies demonstrating the harmful direct impacts of heat on maternal

and newborn health outcomes, including preterm birth, stillbirth, congenital anomalies, preeclampsia, postpartum haemorrhage, foetal distress and long-term impacts on children's health (Chersich et al., 2020, Haghghi et al., 2021, Chersich M et al., 2021). Almost all of these studies were conducted in high-income countries (HICs), leaving no doubt that concerns around heat exposure and adverse MNCH outcomes will not be confined to contexts in low- and lower-middle income countries (LMICs). In fact, effect sizes in sub-Saharan Africa may be even larger than in HICs, the majority of which have temperate climates, growing air conditioning penetrance, and heat-resistant housing. Large parts of sub-Saharan Africa have none of those protective features. Another systematic review by the team (unpublished) located 120 studies documenting the negative effects of extreme heat exposure in children under two years. These first years of life are a unique period of vulnerability – but also a window of opportunity – when the foundations of optimum health, growth, and neurodevelopment across the lifespan are established. A real limitation to date is the lack of research on the impacts of extreme heat throughout pregnancy and a sparse literature base for the African continent and parts of the tropics (MacVicar et al., 2017; Syed et al., 2022).

Good maternal health is crucial for successful birth and neonatal outcomes and requires screening, diagnosing and disease prevention of important conditions that may impact pregnancy. Threats to maternal and perinatal health include short time intervals between pregnancies, unmet nutritional needs, infections, heavy physical labour and underlying chronic conditions like diabetes and obesity, which in turn may complicate pregnancy outcomes, further exacerbated by climate change (Roos et al., 2021). Exposure to high temperatures during pregnancy has a range of physiological effects, including a reduction in placental blood flow due to vasodilation (Wang et al., 2020), and an inflammatory response that may trigger early labour (Samuels et al., 2022). We have found that high ambient temperatures in early pregnancy increase the risk of severe hypertensive disorders (preeclampsia, eclampsia, and HELLP syndrome),

supporting the hypothesis that heat exposure in early pregnancy impairs early placental development (Part et al., 2022).

Women and neonates are among the most vulnerable groups across a range of social and cultural contexts. Identifying pregnant women and neonates as at-risk groups during climate-related events, such as heat extremes, is becoming an emerging need for an adequate policy and public health response to mitigate the risk of heat on adverse MNCH outcomes. Heat exposure and vulnerability to impacts vary widely across geographical areas, population groups, and by socio-economic status.

Designing effective climate policies depends on rigorous quantification and monitoring of heat-related impacts among the most vulnerable, highest-risk groups. Research is required to assess and quantify the differential impacts across settings of climate change and heatwaves on MNCH outcomes. This is particularly needed in low- and middle-income countries where the burden is likely to be the largest and likely to increase over time and in areas with the poorest resources to adapt.

While it is clear that pregnant and postpartum women and infants are heavily affected by climate change, these populations have received little attention to date in climate change policies and public health responses. Health conditions affecting pregnant and postpartum women, fetuses and infants can have lifelong and trans-generational implications, considerably more profound than among other population groups. Understanding and measuring heat impacts in these populations is thus essential for calculating the overall burden of heat-related disease, and for guiding policy choices.

While there is evidence to support pregnant women, infants, and children being vulnerable groups to extreme heat (Roos N et al., 2021, Dalugoda et al., 2022), there is considerable heterogeneity in the analytical methodologies, exposure metrics, and windows of susceptibility examined in the current literature base, which limits synthesis and comparability of findings across studies and contexts. Research to date has primarily focused on mean air temperature as the environmental exposure of interest. However, mean air temperature does not adequately capture the level of

heat stress that a population is exposed to and other environmental exposures (including humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation) should also be taken into account in order to identify meaningful heat thresholds that will inform ENSs to reduce the impacts of heat exposure on MNCH. Heat stress indices are a current methodological approach for improving the accuracy of considering the burden of heat on the body. They include: (i) the Universal Thermal Climate Index, developed as part of a COST action (Fiala et al., 2012, Bröde et al., 2012); (ii) Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT), the current international standard for considering the effects of heat stress on occupational health (ISO, 2017); and apparent temperature, an empirical approximation of the combined effects of air temperature and relative humidity on a human (Steadman, 1984).

There is a lack of monitoring, warning and policy that targets pregnant and postpartum women and infants at all levels, from international to local level (Rowland, 2008; Smith, 2019). It is essential that comparable cross-country analyses are carried out to assess the impacts of extreme heat on the health of these vulnerable groups, including the burden of heat-related disease, to support evidence-based policy making and the implementation of tracking and interventions.

Description of the overarching HIGH Horizons project

The work outlined in this protocol is part of a larger project looking at the impacts of heat and climate change on maternal, neonatal and child health. The four-year (2022-2026) HIGH Horizons project (Figure 23) involves seven partners in Europe, three in Africa, and one international organisation (WHO). The project centres on vulnerable populations affected by climate change: pregnant and postpartum women, infants, and health workers (<https://www.high-horizons.eu/>). HIGH Horizons is funded by the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no 101057843. Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478.

The broader HIGH Horizons project has six main components organised as work packages (WPs), each with specific tasks. The WPs/tasks serve to achieve five project objectives:

1. Identify and select suitable indicators for quantifying and monitoring global, EU, and national-level health impacts of extreme heat.
2. Develop and test an Early Warning Systems (EWS) using a smartphone app to provide individualized and locally adapted heat stress warnings.
3. Identify cost-effective, integrated adaptation-mitigation interventions to alleviate heat impacts on health care workers, and to reduce carbon emissions associated with health care.
4. Support global and EU climate policies and activities on the monitoring of direct and indirect impacts of climate change on health, and the strengthening of Early Warning Systems through guidance documents, and risk assessment and cost-benefit analysis.
5. Investigate the biological and thermal physiological pathways from heat effects on adverse health outcomes among pregnant women and their infants in the first year of life.

Contribution of this sub-study to HIGH Horizons

This study protocol falls within WP2 of HIGH Horizons (assessment of health impacts and facilities), task 2.1 (population-level impacts: measurement).

Analyses of heat-health impacts and data science predictive modelling using population-level data from Sweden, Italy (Lazio region), Greece and data from health facilities in Kenya and South Africa (Gauteng province) underpin all other activities in HIGH Horizons. These analyses, along with systematic reviews, will inform testing and selection of global, EU and national indicators. Analyses will also inform cut-off thresholds for an Early Notification System (ENS), whereby a smartphone app (ClimApp-MCH) will deliver personalised warnings and context-specific messages, co-designed locally.

Figure 23: Outline of the HIGH Horizons project according to work packages

Aim and research objectives

The aim of the epidemiological study is to generate evidence to inform the testing and selection of global, EU and national indicators of heat exposure on maternal, neonatal, and child health (MNCH), and to inform cut-off thresholds for a personalised early warning/early notification system for pregnant and postpartum women, infants and health workers.

The primary objectives are:

- 1) To quantify relationships between ambient temperature exposures and risk of adverse maternal, neonatal, and child health outcomes;
- 2) To identify the relative temperature threshold(s) above which risk of an adverse outcome is increased;
- 3) To determine valid and reliable heat indicators for assessing heat-MNCH impacts at population-level;
- 4) To characterise groups of pregnant women and children at high risk of heat-related conditions;
- 5) To determine if heat-MNCH associations vary by location, climate, facility, or quality of care, as the data allow.

Our secondary objectives are:

- 6) To identify critical windows of susceptibility during gestation or during infancy and childhood;
- 7) To explore impacts of both acute and cumulative heat exposures.

Methods

HIGH Horizons has access to national, regional and facility health datasets in Europe (Greece, Italy and Sweden) and Africa (Kenya and South Africa).

Study design

This study is observational (non-interventional), using data from secondary sources only. No primary data will be collected. All outcomes have already occurred; data on which were collected in electronic form within the country of origin. Collection of data in electronic form occurred either as part of routine care procedures (Rome, Sweden, or Greece), or data were extracted from paper-based records as part of research or surveillance activities (South Africa and Kenya). For child health outcomes longitudinal data will be collected from the Health and Demographic Surveillance Systems (HDSS) through the INDEPTH network, and other datasets which are available openly or through data sharing agreements. We will employ a range of complementary analytical approaches and specific study designs, including time-series and time-stratified case-crossover designs as well as time-to-event techniques, to define the significance value where possible of effect estimates and heat thresholds. The choice of approach will depend on factors such as the outcome, number of cases, availability of data on individual-level confounders, and the exposure window of interest.

The study design allows us to use all available data that meet our inclusion criteria. In the event of rare outcomes for which we do not have adequate statistical power, we will consider evidence-based composite outcomes shown to have a similar biological mechanism. An example is grouping stillbirths and neonatal mortality.

Country climate description

Greece:

Greece is a high-income country and is located in the southernmost part of the Balkan Peninsula. The Greek mainland covers approximately 80% of the total land area while the country and the rest are covered by more than 3000 islands. Significant geographical variations in climate conditions are observed between coastal areas/islands, inland areas and mountainous areas. Greece exhibits a typical Mediterranean climate characterized by mild and wet winters in the

southern lowland and island regions, and colder winters and snowfall in the northern mountainous areas. During winter, mean minimum temperatures range from 5 to 10°C near the coast and from 0 to 5°C over the mainland, while temperatures below 0 ° C are recorded in mountainous areas. From June to August, rainfall is infrequent, and dry conditions prevail, with mean maximum temperatures ranging between 29 and 35°C (<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-011-0219-8>).

Italy:

Italy is a high-income country. Italy has a predominantly Mediterranean climate with mild (sometimes rainy) winters, and hot dry summers. Lazio (Italy) in general has a hot climate. Temperatures during the day are in the range from 12°C (54 °F) in January to 30°C (86 °F) in August. The driest month is July with just 3 days of rain, and the wettest month is November with 12 days of rain.

Sweden:

Sweden is a high-income country. Sweden's proximity to the North Atlantic and prevailing south-westerly to westerly winds result in a climate that is mild in the winter months, but the northernmost part of the country has a sub-Arctic climate with long, cold and snowy winters. There are three different climatic zones in Sweden: the south has an oceanic climate, the centre has a humid continental climate, and the north has a subarctic climate. Summers in the south and centre of Sweden are warm and pleasant, with average temperatures ranging between 13.3°C and 16.6°C.

Kenya:

Kenya is a lower-middle income country. The region of Mombasa has a tropical climate, with temperatures ranging from 21°C to 32°C and average annual rainfall ranging from 300mm to 1200mm (Weatherspark, n.d.). This area

experiences seasonal changes in precipitation and temperatures, which could affect the spread of infectious diseases (Fares, 2013).

South Africa:

South Africa is an upper-middle income country. Johannesburg and Soweto are in the Gauteng province, which is the smallest and most densely populated province in the country. Johannesburg is the provincial capital of Gauteng and the largest city in South Africa, with approximately 5 million inhabitants (Statistics South Africa, 2018). Soweto is a low-income urban settlement to the west of Johannesburg. The catchment area of Soweto study facilities has a population of approximately 1.7 million. The province has a temperate climate with four distinct seasons: Summer (December to February), autumn (March to May), winter (June to August), and spring (September to November). Average daily temperatures range from 15°C to 28°C during the summer, and from 7°C to 18°C during the winter (Part et al., 2022). Winter is the driest season with the highest rainfall in summer.

MNCH data

Country	Coverage	Time period	Number of births
Greece	Nationwide	1999-2021	2,316,655
Italy	Regional (Lazio)	2001-2019	857,145
Sweden	Nationwide	2014-2021	560,615
Kenya	Facility (N=1)	2017-2022	3212
South Africa	Facility (N=11)	2016-2023	220,000
South Africa	Facility (N=1); birth surveillance data	2017-2018	8503

Greece:

- Birth data

The dataset contains information on 2,316,655 births in Greece from 1999 to 2021. Variables concerning each birth include i) stillbirth, ii) cause of stillbirth, iii) person present at birth, iv) gestational weeks v) birth weight in grams, vi) maternal age, vii) mode of delivery, viii) maternal nationality, ix) marital status, x) residence (urban/rural/semi urban), xi) number of newborns. The full date of childbirth (DD/MM/YY) and the municipality of residence of the mother is available for all births. Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT) is the owner of the data.

- Hospitalization data

Nationwide data on hospitalizations of pregnant women from 1999-2015 will be used. The dataset will contain geographically aggregated data on hospitalisation per ICD code falling into the “Pregnancy, childbirth and the puerperium” category (1999-2012: ICD-9, 2014-2015: ICD-10). Similarly, data on hospitalizations of children up to 1 year of age will be acquired.

Italy:

Italian data (for the Lazio Region only) are property of the Lazio Region and will be analysed by the Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service – ASL Roma 1 (hereafter DEP-Lazio). The Certificate of Delivery Care Registry of the Lazio Region (one of the 20 Italian regions, the one where Rome is located) will be used. The database includes births between 2001 and 2019 and a total of about 857,145 births. The regional Register includes information on the type of delivery, clinical status of the baby at birth, and socio-demographic variables of the mother, date of delivery, maternal citizenship, maternal age, educational level, occupational status, municipality of birth, gestational age, birth weight, malformations at birth, singleton or twin delivery, as well as longitude

and latitude of residential address. Through the latter, an index is available to characterize the socio-economic status of the maternal residential area. Furthermore, by linking the mother ID to the hospital discharge files or drug prescription files, we can get info about pre-existing or later admissions as well as drug prescriptions of the mother.

Sweden:

The Swedish Pregnancy Register (SPR) covers more than 92% of births in Sweden and provides high quality data for research in pregnancy and early childhood as well as quality of care improvement (Stephansson et al., 2018). Data are available from January 1, 2014, to December 31, 2019 and includes 560,615 births. Information on each pregnancy is available from the woman's first visit to antenatal care to their postnatal follow-up visit at around 8-16 weeks postpartum. The majority of data is collected directly from electronic medical records (Stephansson et al., 2018). Each individual in Sweden has a unique identifier assigned at birth or immigration and is used to link the pregnant woman in the SPR with the National Patient Register (for maternal and neonatal health outcomes) (Ludvigsson et al., 2011), and Statistics Sweden for socioeconomic and residential address information (de Bont et al., 2022).

Kenya:

The dataset comprises of 3212 births from the Aga Khan Hospital in Mombasa and its delivery wards. It covers the period 2017 to 2022. Key outcomes included in this dataset are for example: duration of labour, mother health during labour, mother HIV status, mode of delivery, APGAR score, mode of delivery (including type of caesarean section), birth weight, birth outcome/child condition at birth.

South Africa:

- Soweto surveillance data

The Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics Research Unit of the University of the Witwatersrand, led by Professor Shabir Madhi, funds and maintains a passive surveillance (birth register) dataset for the Soweto region of South Africa.

Information is recorded on all deliveries at midwife-led clinics and tertiary referral hospital in the region (N = 10), including date of admission, date and time of delivery, maternal characteristics (age, parity, gravidity, nationality), morbidities (e.g. maternal HIV status) and complications at birth, number of infants born, mode of delivery (normal vaginal delivery, caesarean section), assisted delivery (vacuum extraction, forceps), caesarean section (emergency, elective), reason for caesarean section, duration of delivery (HH:MM), gestational age at delivery (completed weeks), birth outcome (live born, fresh stillbirth, macerated stillbirth), infant characteristics (sex, birth weight, head circumference, length), APGAR score at 5 minutes and 10 minutes of life, and condition of the child (transferred to mother, transferred to nursery, died, other). The database includes approximately 220 000 births between April 2016 and March 2023. It is estimated that this dataset includes 98% of births that occurred in Soweto during this period (Statistics South Africa, 2020).

- Inner city Johannesburg birth register data

Maternal health, demographic, and obstetric history data were collected from birth registries to include all births between 01 July 2017 and 30 June 2018 at one tertiary referral hospital in inner city Johannesburg. Data were originally collected as part of a population-based observational medical record review study, led by collaborators at Wits RHI. Approximately 8500 women deliver in this hospital annually. It serves inner city Johannesburg and surrounding suburban areas, receiving referrals from primary care and secondary level facilities for high-risk

deliveries. Information is available for each birth (n=8503), including antepartum complications / reason for referral (e.g. diabetes, preeclampsia, antepartum haemorrhage, prelabour rupture of the membranes), gestational age at delivery, mode of delivery and indication for emergency caesarean section (e.g. foetal distress), duration of labour, postpartum complications (e.g. distress, infection, postpartum haemorrhage), transfer of mother (e.g. to intensive care unit), maternal HIV status, infant status at birth (e.g. alive, intrapartum stillbirth, antepartum stillbirth), birth weight, infant complications (e.g. birth asphyxia, respiratory distress), transfer of infant (e.g. to NICU), APGAR score, congenital anomalies (e.g. hydrocephalus), etc.

Priority health outcomes

For cross-country analyses, we will prioritise MNCH outcomes that are available in all datasets (outlined below), which will enable the comparison of temperature and heat effect estimates across settings. We have also prepared a more extensive list of MNCH outcomes that are available in one or more datasets (see Annex 10) and which we hypothesise to be affected by heat exposure. In addition to the priority outcomes, individual teams will assess the impacts of high temperature and extreme heat on a range of MNCH outcomes available within their respective datasets.

All health outcome variables must include the full date (DD/MM/YY) of event (i.e. diagnosis or delivery) and location of residence or name of birthing facility to enable linkage with exposure data.

Perinatal health

- *Gestational age at birth*: Completed weeks of gestation at birth (continuous measure) using best estimate available (e.g., LMP or second trimester ultrasound for gestational dating).

- *Preterm birth*: Delivery of a live born infant at less than 37 weeks' gestation (based on best estimate – see above).
 - *Moderately preterm*: Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 32 and < 37 weeks' gestation.
 - *Very preterm*: Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 28 and < 32 weeks' gestation.
 - *Extremely preterm*: Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 22 and < 28 weeks' gestation.
- *Stillbirth*: Foetal death prior to the complete expulsion of the foetus
 - *Intrapartum (fresh) stillbirth*: Foetal death immediately before or during labour with no signs of maceration (intact skin) after 22 or 28 gestational weeks
 - *Antepartum (macerated) stillbirth*: Foetal death before labour with signs of maceration (discolouration and peeling of the skin) after 22 or 28 gestational weeks.
- *Birth weight*: Weight of baby at birth in grams (continuous measure).
- *Low birth weight*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing less than 2500 grams.
 - *Moderately low birth weight*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 1500 to < 2500 grams.
 - *Very low birth weight*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 1000 to < 1500 grams.
 - *Extremely low birth weight*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing < 1000 grams.
- *Small for gestational age*: below 10th percentile of birth weight for gestational age and sex (Lawn et al., 2023)
- *Macrosomia*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 4500 grams.
- APGAR score at 5 minutes after birth (ordinal measure, 1-10).

- *Low APGAR score*: APGAR score of <7 at 5 minutes of age.
- *Interfacility transfer*: Transfer of newborn to neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) or other specialised ward/unit for complication.

Maternal health

- Mode of delivery:
 - Vaginal birth
 - Assisted vaginal birth (e.g. by forceps or vacuum extraction)
 - Caesarean section (C-section)
 - Any C-section
 - Emergency C-section
 - Elective C-section
- Duration of labour (HH:MM)
- *Interfacility transfer*: Transfer of woman to intensive care unit (ICU) or other specialised ward/unit for complication.

Child health

- *Hospitalisation*: Admission to hospital, all cause
- Mortality
 - *Neonatal mortality*: born alive with death (all cause) between 0-28 days.
 - *Infant mortality*: Death (all cause) before one year of life.
 - *Under-five mortality*: Death (all cause) before 5 years of life.

Meteorological data

Hourly ERA5 reanalysis data, which is a combination of observations and mathematical models to create global coverage for meteorological data, were obtained from the Copernicus Climate Data Store for the variables of air temperature (air temperature), 2m dew point temperature, 10m u component of

wind, 10m v component of wind and 5 radiation variables: *surface solar radiation downwards, surface net solar radiation, surface thermal radiation downwards, total sky direct solar radiation at surface and surface net thermal radiation*. This data is on a 0.25x0.25 grid and obtained for 1991-2022. To consider air pollution, reanalysis data provided by the CAMS data store maintained by ECMWF is obtained for the variables of: *ozone, particulate matter (<1, <10 and <2.5) and nitrogen dioxide*. This data is on a 0.75x0.75 grid and obtained for 2003 to end of 2022. Finally, all data is aggregated to a daily minimum, maximum and mean temporal scale.

The exposures that will be explored include daily maximum, minimum and mean temperature, apparent temperature, universal thermal climate index (UTCI) and wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT). Other exposures to be explored include relative humidity and diurnal temperature range (i.e. daily maximum minus minimum temperature). In collaboration with ECMWF (The European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts), wind speed and the heat stress indices of apparent temperature, heat index, UTCI, WBGT, and surface relative humidity were created using the methodology described in the *thermofeel* python library.

Data processing and analyses

All data processing and analyses will be conducted using R (version 4.1.1 or later), facilitated by RStudio, or Python (version 3.8).

Exposures will be assigned to each woman or infant in each dataset by time (e.g. date of health event, delivery, conception) and place (residential address or location of birthing facility).

Epidemiological analyses

Advanced regression techniques will be used to fulfil our research objectives, including time-series analysis, time-to-event analysis, conditional logistic regression, quantile regression, and machine learning methodologies.

In time-series analysis, outcomes will be aggregated to daily counts. Conditional quasi-Poisson or negative binomial regression will be used, depending on the degree of overdispersion commonly seen in such data. In the event that negative binomial models do not account for the overdispersion (due to many days with zero outcomes), we will use zero-inflated Poisson or negative binomial models. Spline terms will be used to adjust for season and long-term trends. Cross-basis functions will be used to characterise the nonlinear and delayed effects of temperature following a distributed lag nonlinear model (DLNM) framework.

Time-to-event analysis will be used when there is censoring in the data, when the time-to-event is an outcome of interest (e.g. gestational age at diagnosis of preeclampsia), and/or when it is important to control for gestational age (e.g. for preterm birth, the likelihood of an outcome increases as gestational age increases from 22 to 36 weeks (de Bont et al., 2022)). We will fit Cox proportional hazards models with gestational age as the timescale (Schifano et al., 2016), and combine with DLNMs to capture any nonlinear or delayed effects of heat exposure. Frailty terms will account for clustering in the data. Models will adjust for individual risk factors (e.g. maternal age) as well as time-varying factors (e.g. season, humidity).

We will use a time-stratified case-crossover design when there is limited data on individual-level confounders and when we hypothesise an acute effect of heat on the outcome of interest. Here, a person's exposure levels on the day of the health event ("case day") is compared with that same person's exposure levels on proximate days when the health event did not occur ("control days"), thereby

implicitly controlling for confounding factors that are fixed (or vary slowly) over time (Lu and Zeger, 2006, Tobias A et al., 2014). Control days will be selected following the time-stratified strategy: For each case, controls will be defined as the same day of the week within the same month and year (providing 3-4 controls per case). We will combine conditional logistic regression (strata, woman ID) with DLNMs to capture nonlinear and delayed effects of temperature and extreme heat (up to 6 days before the health outcome).

We will use quantile regression when the outcome of interest is a continuous measure, e.g. gestational age at delivery in completed weeks, or birth weight in grams. Here, we will estimate the effect of high ambient temperature and extreme heat on specific quantiles of the continuous outcome distribution. The specific quantiles will be based on the cut-off points that are used to define the adverse outcome, or categories of that adverse outcome, e.g. preterm birth categories (at 28, 32, and 37 weeks of gestation) or low birth weight categories (at 1000, 1500 and 2500 grams).

We will explore the influence of high temperature and extreme heat at different time periods (or lags) preceding the event. This approach reflects the potential biological pathways through which temperature can influence MNCH outcomes, where, for example, exposure to extreme heat at week 32 of pregnancy may result in a preterm birth on that same day or, more commonly, a few days thereafter. The lag structure in our models will be based on existing evidence for each temperature-outcome relationship, where possible. For example, our previous findings from South Africa show that high temperatures in early pregnancy (2-5 weeks' gestation) are associated with an increased risk of severe hypertensive disorders (Part et al., 2022).

Further, we will employ the use of machine learning modelling to explore the influence of high temperature and extreme heat on health outcomes, including

the possibility to include lag times. This approach has been used in previous studies across the health field (Wiemken and Kelley, 2020). For example, a study that compared machine learning methodology to logistic regression for predicting preeclampsia as an outcome found multiple machine learning models to outperform the traditional approach (Zheng et al., 2022). A UK cohort study also used machine learning to assess what health and socio-economic factors are the most important in predicting preterm birth (Waynforth, 2022). Types of models that will be used here include methods from both regression and classification such as Convolutional Neural Nets (CNNs), Gradient Descent, Random Forests and Bayesian.

Subgroup analyses

We will conduct a series of subgroup analyses to characterise those women and children at greatest risk of adverse heat effects. Findings will inform the personalised early notification system. As the data allow, we will stratify by maternal characteristics (e.g. age at delivery, parity, socioeconomic status, education level, BMI, smoking), comorbidities (e.g. diabetes, HIV, chronic hypertension), infant characteristics (e.g. sex, birth weight categories). Where there is insufficient power due to small population size within sub-groups, we will test for interaction effects (temperature and maternal/infant characteristics) on the outcome of interest.

Where possible, we will also stratify by region and birthing facility type (e.g. tertiary referral hospital, midwife-led clinic).

Pooling temperature effects

Country-specific effects (coefficients and standard errors) will be meta-analysed using the inverse variance method. Fixed-effects and random-effects will be applied using restricted maximum likelihood to estimate between-region variance and Q-profile to estimate 95% confidence intervals.

Data management

With the exception of data from South Africa and Kenya, which will be analysed at LSHTM respectively UNI GRAZ following a Data Sharing Agreement, each site will analyse their respective country data according to the analyses plan generated by the core statistical team. Data will be compared across countries when considered valid, but data will NOT be pooled. Data management will be carried out in accordance with the HIGH Horizons Data Management Plan, dated 30 November 2022. In accordance with this plan, our data management has the following characteristics:

- Each partner will store the data on its institutional network, on a secure server protected by two-level authentication.
- Data storage on local devices will be avoided at all times. If storing a copy of the data on local machines is necessary (e.g., the study statistician), then the data will be password-protected and only include de-identified data.
- Access to data will be restricted to a limited number of study staff that have appropriate training to manage data.
- Non-personal data (e.g., environmental or ambient temperature data) will be made openly available unless sourced from a commercial source.
- Data ownership will be with the country teams in South Africa, Kenya, Greece, Italy, and Sweden or relevant Data Sharing Agreements will be put in place.
- All data will be stored in accordance with GDPR legislation and recognised data security standards for a minimum number of years according to each country's requirements. For example, In the UK, data will be stored on the secure server at LSHTM for a minimum of 10 years after project completion or publication date (whichever is longest) unless the data providers request that we delete the data.

Dissemination and communication of findings

The preliminary findings from this population-level heat-health impacts study will be reported in Deliverable 2.3 'Heat-health analysis report from Italian, Swedish and African data 1', due end of November 2023. The findings related to all objectives will be reported in Deliverable D2.4 'Heat-health analysis report from Italian, Swedish and African data 2', due end of August 2025.

The results of will inform other tasks within the HIGH Horizons project:

- The results from primary objective 1 will inform the WHO Expert Group on Indicators and the development of heat-related indicators for monitoring and surveillance purposes;
- The findings from primary objectives 2 and 3 will inform the Early Notification System.

HIGH Horizons has a detailed Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan (dated Feb 2023). Apart from the report (deliverable D2.3), the results of this study will be disseminated through a range of media. In addition to peer-reviewed journal papers, we will publish accessible summaries of the research findings. The HIGH Horizons consortium will promote the research findings through the project website and social media platforms, including LinkedIn and Twitter. We will present at international conferences in environmental health and maternal and neonatal health.

Ethical considerations

This study encompasses analyses of data that have already been collected in the aforementioned countries. Data will be accessed and used in accordance with the agreed design of the study, requirements of the data providers, and in compliance with legal, ethical, regulatory, funding body, and institutional requirements. Before data are shared for analyses, they will undergo

anonymisation appropriate to the needs of the study. No case report forms, treatment records, or files linking participant ID codes with participant names will be shared.

The datasets will be saved using a file compression application, which allows the data to be password-protected. The data will then be shared using a time-limited, password-protected online file sharing service. In the event that data must be analysed on a local device, data files will be encrypted and temporarily stored on a password-protected computer, in accordance with the requirements specified by the data providers, to ensure confidentiality of participant information and to protect against data loss and corruption. Once data have been analysed, they will be permanently removed from the device.

No individuals will be identifiable from any publications or reports produced from this study. Results will be presented on an aggregated level only.

Obtaining informed written consent from participants is not feasible. We will therefore request a waiver of informed consent on the basis that: (i) the proposed study presents no more than minimal risk to participants; (ii) no participant will be identifiable from any reports or publications produced from the proposed study; and (iii) this study, which aims to reduce the impacts of climate change on MNCH, is not feasible without a waiver of consent.

All participating sites will obtain approval from relevant **local ethics committees**:

- For South Africa: University of the Witwatersrand Human Research Ethics Committee;
- For analysis of South African data by LSHTM: LSHTM Observational Research Ethics Committee (UK);
- For Greece: Research Ethics Committee (University of Thessaly, Greece);

- For Italy, data access and usage are regulated by regional and national laws. DEP-Lazio is entitled to use and analyse data for epidemiological purposes (being part of its institutional mandate) but it is not allowed to share any individual data;
- For Sweden: National Ethical Review Committee (Etikprövningsmyndigheten) in Sweden;
- For Kenya: Aga Khan University Research Ethics Committee;
- For analysis of Kenyan data by UNI Graz: Research Ethics Committee (University of Graz, Austria).

Timeline

	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025
Protocol development								
SCC and ethical approvals								
Data sharing								
Data preparation								
Analyses								
Write up								

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Sub-Annex: Long list for selection of priority outcomes

OUTCOMES - Variable Generic Name
Maternal health outcomes - from original EU protocol list
Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy occurring after 20 weeks' gestation
<i>Pregnancy-induced hypertension: Systolic blood pressure >140 mmHg and diastolic blood pressure > 90 mmHg</i>
<i>Preeclampsia: Systolic/diastolic blood pressure > 140/90 mmHg and 24-hour proteinuria ≥ 0.3 g, haematological or biochemical abnormalities, and/or intrauterine growth restriction</i>
<i>Eclampsia: Severe form of preeclampsia characterised by seizures</i>
Diabetes
<i>Gestational diabetes</i>
<i>Diabetes mellitus type 1 and type 2</i>
Dehydration
Maternal stress
Premature rupture of the membranes (PROM)
Compromised placental development and/or function
<i>Placental abruption</i>
<i>Placenta previa</i>
<i>Placental insufficiency</i>
<i>Other placental disorders (accreta, etc.)</i>
Haemorrhage
<i>Antenatal haemorrhage</i>
<i>Postpartum haemorrhage: severe vaginal bleeding after childbirth (between delivery and 6 weeks postpartum) of ≥ 1000 ml of blood loss</i>
Renal disease
Caesarean section (C-section):
<i>Any C-Section</i>
<i>Emergency C-section</i>
<i>Planned C-section</i>
<i>C-Section unknown type</i>
Heat stroke or heat-related illness, heat strain
Instrumental delivery (vacuum extraction or forceps)
Additional from conceptual framework
Maternal Fever during pregnancy, childbirth and the postpartum period
Endocrine system dysfunction
Mental Health
Additional available in dataset(s)
HIV Status
Labour Duration (HH:MM)
Interfacility Transfer
Assisted Delivery

Normal Vaginal Delivery
Indication for C-Section
Any hospitalization
Chronic Hypertension
Urinary tract infection (UTI) - this includes cystitis and pyelonephritis during pregnancy and the postpartum period.
Malaria
Duration of Hospital Stay (delivery)
Labour Induction
Asthma
Mastitis
Perinatal health outcomes - from original EU protocol list
Miscarriage (available query)
Stillbirth: Foetal death prior to the complete expulsion of the foetus
<i>Intrapartum (fresh) stillbirth: Foetal death immediately before or during labour with no signs of maceration (intact skin) after 22 gestational weeks</i>
<i>Antepartum (macerated) stillbirth: Foetal death before labour with signs of maceration (discolouration and peeling of the skin) after 22 gestational weeks.</i>
<i>Foetal death Unspecified timing</i>
Foetal distress during childbirth
Meconium aspiration
Congenital malformation
Additional available in dataset(s)
Infant Sex (Gender)
Newborn health outcomes - from original EU protocol list
Newborn Mortality: born alive with death between 0-28 days
Gestational age at birth: Completed weeks of gestation at birth (continuous measure)
Preterm birth: Delivery of a live born infant at less than 37 weeks' gestation
<i>Moderately preterm: Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 32 and < 37 weeks' gestation</i>
<i>Very preterm: Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 28 and < 32 weeks' gestation</i>
<i>Extremely preterm: Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 22 and < 28 weeks' gestation</i>
Birth weight: Weight of baby at birth in grams (continuous measure)
Low birth weight: Delivery of a live born infant weighing less than 2500 grams
<i>Moderately low birth weight: Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 1500 to < 2500 grams</i>
<i>Very low birth weight: Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 1000 to < 1500 grams</i>
<i>Extremely low birth weight: Delivery of a live born infant weighing < 1000 grams</i>
Hospital admissions
<i>NICU admission at birth</i>
<i>Any Hospital admission post-discharge</i>

Jaundice
INR alterations
Feeding practices
<i>Breastfeeding initiation: Time to first breastfeed</i>
<i>Prelacteal feeding: Any solid or liquid foods, including water, other than breast milk during the first 24 hours after birth</i>
<i>Exclusive breastfeeding: No solid or liquid foods, include water, other than breast milk given in past 24 hours</i>
<i>Mixed feeding: breast milk plus any other solid or liquid foods, including water in the past 24 hours</i>
<i>Breastmilk substitute only in the past 24 hours</i>
Intrauterine growth restriction (this is gestational age and sex standardized and may not be available in all countries)
Birth asphyxia
Additional from conceptual framework
Neonatal fever
Additional available in dataset(s)
Infant Sex (Gender)
Apgar Score (1m, 5min and 10Min)
PMTCT/ARV
Interfacility transfer
Infant Resuscitation
Large for gestational age
Duration of hospital stay (days)
Child health outcomes - from original EU protocol list
Mortality
<i>Infant Mortality (0-12 months): Death (all cause) before one year of life</i>
<i>Child Mortality (0-59 months): Death (all cause) before 5th birthday</i>
<i>Child Mortality (1-59 months): Death (all cause) from 1 month to before 5th birthday</i>
Respiratory disease (including asthma)
<i>Acute respiratory illness (ARI): fast breathing without fever</i>
<i>Acute respiratory illness (ARI): fast breathing with fever</i>
<i>Pneumonia: diagnosed</i>
<i>Asthma</i>
<i>Respiratory disease: unspecified</i>
Malnutrition
<i>Wasting: Low weight for height</i>
<i>Stunting: Low height for weight</i>
<i>Underweight: low weight for age</i>
<i>MUAC</i>
Bacterial infections
Heat stroke or heat illness

Emergency department visits
Unintentional injuries
Dehydration
Fewer days of schooling
Lower educational attainment
Additional from conceptual framework
Fever
Care seeking for ARI
Care seeking for Fever
Other common outcomes
Diarrhoeal Disease
Malaria
HIV
TB
Hospitalization
Developmental Disability
Anaemia
Other common outcomes (not likely in EMR/HMIS)
Minimum Dietary Diversity (MDD)
Minimum Acceptable Diet (MAD)
Air Pollution attributable Death
<i>Ambient Air Pollution attributable death 0-5 years</i>
<i>Indoor Air Pollution attributable death 0-5 years</i>
Climate Change attributable death
Additional available in dataset(s)
Child Sex (Gender)

COVARIATES - Variable Generic Name
Health Services Coverage/Outcomes (from client records)
Antenatal Coverage
<i>ANC Any</i>
<i>ANC 4+ visits</i>
<i>ANC 8 visits+</i>
<i>No ANC/ANC Unk</i>
Delivery Site
<i>Health Facility</i>
<i>Home</i>
<i>In Transit</i>
<i>Unknown</i>
Skilled Birth Attendant
Postnatal Visit Mom within 2 days
Postnatal Visit Newborn within 2 days

Modern Family Planning Method
Immigrant (Sweden, Greece, Italy)
Children aged <5 years with diarrhoea receiving ORS
Children aged <5 years with malaria receiving ACT
Childhood Immunizations
Health System Structural (from facility surveys)
Human Resources for Health
CHW coverage
Cold Chain integrity
Essential Medicine Availability
Access within X hours to PHC Facility
Distance to Health Facility
Facility Power Supply
Facility Water Supply
Facility Sanitation Supply
Facility Handwashing
Demographic/biologic factors (from client records)
Age of Mother
Race of Mother
Ethnicity of Mother
Gravidity of Mother
Parity of Mother
Mother has Chronic Disease
Immigrant (Sweden, Greece, Italy)
Marital Status
Educational level
Socio-economic factors
Wealth Quintile
Food Security
Religion
Housing Type
Water Source
Sanitation
Handwashing
Indoor Air Pollution
Household Assets

Geographical factors
Ambient Air Pollution
Risk Factors and Transmission
<i>Food-born</i>
<i>Air-born</i>
<i>Vector-born</i>
PHE Affected (e.g. Ebola, Zika)
Community SES
Socio-Political Factors
Conflict Affected
Natural Disaster Affected
Local Social Structures

9.2 Appendix B: Codes

```
#####  
#####  
# SEPT 2023  
# PREPARE DATA FOR CASE-CROSSOVER  
# Cherie Part (LSHTM)  
#####  
#####  
# load packages  
install.packages("pacman")  
pacman::p_load(dplyr,magrittr,data.table)  
  
# import data  
df <- read.csv(".csv")  
  
# format date  
df$date <- as.Date(df$date, format="%Y-%m-%d")  
  
# year, month, day, day of week  
df %<>% mutate(year = lubridate::year(date),  
               month = lubridate::month(date),  
               dow = as.factor(weekdays(date)))  
  
# RESTRICT DATA TO CASES  
# stillbirth  
sb <- df[which(df$sb == 1), ]  
  
# order by date  
sb <- sb[order(sb$date), ]  
  
# ADD CONTROL ROWS FOR EACH CASE - same dow in same month and year  
# create dataframe of all dates  
alldates <- data.frame(date=seq(as.Date("2016-04-01"),  
                               as.Date("2022-03-31"),  
                               by='days'))  
  
# add year, month and dow  
alldates %<>% mutate(year = lubridate::year(date),  
                   month = lubridate::month(date),  
                   dow = as.factor(weekdays(date)))  
  
# convert to data table  
setDT(alldates)  
  
# convert outcome data to table  
sb_dt <- setDT(sb)  
  
# insert new rows  
sb_dt1 <- alldates[sb_dt[, .(index, facility, mage_gp, mpar_gp,  
                           mode, mhiv, term, isex_new, ga_new,  
                           sb=0L, fsb=0L, msb=0L, year, month, dow)],  
# include all required variables  
  
# outcomes=0 in new rows  
on=.(year, month, dow), allow.cartesian=TRUE][  
  sb_dt, on=.(index, date=date), sb := i.sb][  
  
# sb = stillbirth
```

```

        sb_dt, on=.(index, date=date), fsb := i.fsb][
# fsb = fresh stillbirth
        sb_dt, on=.(index, date=date), msb := i.msb][]
# msb = macerated stillbirth

# convert to dataframe
sb1 <- as.data.frame(sb_dt1)

# NOW LINK EXPOSURE DATA

#####
#####
# OCTOBER 2023
# TEMPERATURE AND STILLBIRTH - CASE-CROSSOVER DESIGN
# Cherie Part (LSHTM)
#####
#####

# LOAD PACKAGES
pacman::p_load(dplyr, MASS, survival, magrittr, tibble, data.table, dlnm, splines, AICcmodavg)

# SET DIRECTORY
setwd("...")

# IMPORT STILLBIRTH DATA
df <- read.csv("../\sb_cc.csv") # already prepared for CC, with case
and control days

# set date class
df$date <- as.Date(df$date, format = "%Y-%m-%d")

# CALCULATE MEAN DEWPOINT DEPRESSION ACROSS LAGS 0-6
df$dpd06 <- apply(df[34:40], 1, mean) # change column numbers as needed

# CREATE SEPARATE DATASETS FOR allSB, iSB and aSB
# allSB
allsb_ids <- unique(df$id[df$sb==1])
dfs <- subset(df, id %in% allsb_ids)
# iSB
isb_ids <- unique(df$id[df$isb==1])
dfi <- subset(df, id %in% isb_ids)
# aSB
asb_ids <- unique(df$id[df$asb==1])
dfa <- subset(df, id %in% asb_ids)

# order data by id
dfs <- dfs[order(dfs$id), ]
dfi <- dfi[order(dfi$id), ]
dfa <- dfa[order(dfa$id), ]

# SET DEFAULT FOR NAs TO na.exclude
# NA's excluded in estimation but re-inserted in
prediction/residuals
options(na.action="na.exclude")

```

```

#####
# STILLBIRTH
#####
# CONDITIONAL LOGISTIC REGRESSION - LAGS 0-6 DAY
# extract temp matrix
Tavs <- as.matrix(dfi[, c("Tav0", "Tav1",
                        "Tav2", "Tav3",
                        "Tav4", "Tav5", "Tav6")])

# define crossbasis # SHOULD BE INFORMED BY INITIAL EXPLORATION OF
ASSOCIATIONS
#           E.G. SCATTERPLOT OF DAILY MEAN TEMP VS DAILY
STILLBIRTH COUNTS/RATE
#           AND DAILY MEAN TEMP VS RESIDUALS OF DAILY
STILLBIRTH COUNTS/RATE (AFTER REMOVING TRENDS/SEASONAL PATTERN)
# spline with 1 knot for lag, spline with 1 internal knot for var
cbs2 <- crossbasis(Tavs,lag=6,
                  argvar=list(fun="ns", df=2),
                  arglag=list(fun="ns", knots=logknots(6, 1),int=T))
# spline with 1 knot for lag, spline with 2 internal knots for var
cbs3 <- crossbasis(Tavs,lag=6,
                  argvar=list(fun="ns", df=3),
                  arglag=list(fun="ns", knots=logknots(6, 1),int=T))
# spline with 1 knot for lag, spline with 3 internal knots for var
cbs4 <- crossbasis(Tavs,lag=6,
                  argvar=list(fun="ns", df=4),
                  arglag=list(fun="ns", knots=logknots(6, 1),int=T))
# spline with 1 knot for lag, var spline knots at 10th and 90th
percentiles
# import temperature data
td <- read.csv("../temp.csv")
# set date format
td$date <- as.Date(td$date, format = "%d/%m/%Y")
# calculate mean temperature at lag 0 across all relevant grid
cells to calculate percentiles
td$TmeanB <- rowMeans(td[,
c("Tav0_11", "Tav0_12", "Tav0_13", "Tav0_14")], na.rm=TRUE)
# calculate quantiles
quantile(td$TmeanB, c(0.1,0.9))
cbs19 <- crossbasis(Tavs,lag=6,
                  argvar=list(fun="ns", knots=c(25.6,29)), # SPECIFY
TEMPERATURE KNOTS
                  arglag=list(fun="ns", knots=logknots(6, 1),int=T))
# spline with 2 knots for lag, spline with 2 internal knots for var
cbs12 <- crossbasis(Tavs,lag=6,
                  argvar=list(fun="ns", df=3),
                  arglag=list(fun="ns", knots=logknots(6, 2),int=T))
# linear terms for lag and var
cbslin <- crossbasis(Tavs,lag=6,
                  argvar=list(fun="lin"),
                  arglag=list(fun="lin",int=T))

# run models
# adjustment for mean dew point depression (humidity), averaged
over 0-6 day lag, using spline with 1 internal knot
mods2 <- clogit(sb ~ cbs2 + ns(dpd06, df=2) + strata(id), dfs)
mods3 <- clogit(sb ~ cbs3 + ns(dpd06, df=2) + strata(id), dfs)

```

```

mods4 <- clogit(sb ~ cbs4 + ns(dpd06, df=2) + strata(id), dfs)
mods19 <- clogit(sb ~ cbs19 + ns(dpd06, df=2) + strata(id), dfs)
modsl2 <- clogit(sb ~ cbsl2 + ns(dpd06, df=2) + strata(id), dfs)
modslin <- clogit(sb ~ cbslin + ns(dpd06, df=2) + strata(id), dfs)

#define list of models
models <- list(mods2, mods3, mods4, mods19, modsl2, modslin)

#specify model names
mod.names <- c("mods2", "mods3", "mods4", "mods19", "modsl2",
"modslin")

#calculate AIC of each model
aictab(cand.set = models, modnames = mod.names)

# BEST FITTING MODEL IS XXX

# PREDICTIONS
# BEST FITTING MODEL FOR SB
# centred at median to begin with
quantiles <- quantile(td$TmeanB, c(.05, .10, .50, .90, .95))
procen <- as.numeric(round(quantiles[3], digits = 1))
cp <- crosspred(cbs3, mods3, cen=procen, by=0.1)
# create dataframe of predicted effects per 0.1C temp
p <- as.data.frame(cbind(cp$predvar,cp$allRRfit))
# identify temp of minimum stillbirth risk
tms <- p$V1[which.min(p$V2)]

# predictions centred at TMS per 0.5C
preds06tmi <- crosspred(cbs3, mods3, cen=tms, by=0.5)

# PLOT EFFECT
# overall
plot(preds06tmi, "overall",
      ylab="OR of SB",
      xlab=expression(paste("Daily mean temperature (",degree,"C)")),
      cex.axis=1.5, cex.lab=1.75, lwd=2.5,
      ci.arg=list(density=100,col=grey(0.7)))
# at lag 0
plot(preds06tmi, "slices", lag=0,
      ylab="OR of SB",
      xlab=expression(paste("Daily mean temperature (",degree,"C)")),
      cex.axis=1.5, cex.lab=1.75, lwd=2.5,
      ci.arg=list(density=100,col=grey(0.7)))

##### END #####

```

```

#####
#####
# OCTOBER 2023
# D2.3 Analysis Code
# Chloe Brimicombe (UGraz)
#####
#####

#Import Packages
require(dlnm)
require(splines)
require(forecast)
require(tseries)
require(dplyr)
require(ggplot2)

#Function to make a distributed lag and plot
dlnmrrwithplot <- function(df,heat,outcome,cen){
  b <- onebasis(heat, "poly")
  model <- glm(outcome ~ b,family=quasipoisson(), df)
  pred <- crosspred(b, model,cen=cen) #lag = 1,2,3 etc.
  plot(pred, xlab="", ylab="", main="")
}

#function to make a distributed lag and return a dataframe
dlnmrr <- function(df,heat,outcome,cen){
  b <- onebasis(heat, "poly")
  model <- glm(outcome ~ b,family=quasipoisson(), df)
  pred <- crosspred(b, model,cen=cen)
  x1 <- seq(median(heat,na.rm=TRUE),min(heat,na.rm=TRUE),by=-0.1)
  x2 <- seq(median(heat,na.rm=TRUE),max(heat,na.rm=TRUE),by=0.1)
  x1 <- sort(x1)
  x1 <- round(x1,digits=1)
  x2 <- round(x2,digits=1)
  xall <- c(head(x1,-1),x2)
  #xall <- c(head(x1,-1),head(x2,-1)) #head(x2,-1)
  df2 <- data.frame(index = xall,
                    RR = pred$allRRfit,
                    low = pred$allRRlow,
                    high = pred$allRRhigh)

  return(df2)
}

#function to calculate the relative risk and return a dataframe
#at a given percentile (i.e. 95th)

dlnmrrq <- function(df,heat,outcome,cen,percentile,country){
  b <- onebasis(heat, "poly")
  model <- glm(outcome ~ b,family=quasipoisson(), df)
  pred <- crosspred(b, model,cen=cen, at = quantile(heat,
                                                    percentile,
                                                    na.rm = TRUE))

  #xall <- c(head(x1,-1),head(x2,-1)) #head(x2,-1)
  xall <- quantile(heat,0.95,na.rm = TRUE)
  xmedian <- median(heat,na.rm=TRUE)
  se <- (pred$allRRhigh - pred$allRRlow) / (2 * 1.96)
  z <- pred$allRRfit / se

```

```

p <- exp(-0.717*z - 0.416 * z^2)

df2 <- data.frame( index = xall,
                  median = xmedian,
                  RR = pred$allRRfit,
                  low = pred$allRRlow,
                  high = pred$allRRhigh,
                  pvalue = p,
                  country = country)

return(df2)
}

#function to plot dose-response curve from a dataframe

plotfunction <- function(df,xlab,ylab,title,colour){
  ggplot(data=df,aes(x=index,y=RR))+
    geom_hline(yintercept=1)+
    geom_ribbon(aes(ymin=low,ymax=high),alpha=0.2,fill=colour)+
    geom_line()+
    scale_x_continuous(breaks=(seq(min(df$index),max(df$index),by=1)))+
    theme_classic()+theme(text =
element_text(size=12),legend.position="none")+
  xlab(xlab)+ylab(ylab)+ggtitle(title)
}

#code to plot odds risk ratio comparisons
df <- data.frame(Indicator = c("Temperature","WBGT","UTCI","Heat
Index",
                            "Temperature","WBGT",
                            "Temperature","WBGT","UTCI","Temperature"),
                Country =
c("Greece","Greece","Greece","Greece","Italy",
  "Italy","Sweden","Sweden","Sweden","South
Africa"),
                mean = c(16.64,18.64,16.14,16.30,15.8,14,8,7,1,20.5),
                percentile =
c(27.92,27.33,28.89,27.85,25.8,23,18,17,18,22.5),
                odds =
c(1.083,1.091,1.086,1.098,1.098,1.11,1.10,1.10,1.11),
                low =
c(1.044,1.051,1.048,1.047,1.024,1.024,1.01,1.00,1.00,1.04),
                high =
c(1.125,1.132,1.126,1.127,1.179,1.179,1.23,1.21,1.21,1.19))

df$groups = paste(df$Indicator, df$Country, df$percentile, "vs",
df$mean)
df$groups = factor(df$groups, levels=rev(df$groups))

p1 <- ggplot(df, aes(x=groups, y=odds, color=Indicator)) +
  geom_point(size = 3) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 1)+
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = low, ymax = high),linewidth=1.25)+
  coord_flip(clip='off') +
  scale_color_brewer(palette = "Set1")+
  theme_bw()+

```

```

theme(text = element_text(size=12))+
theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5))+
xlab("Countries and Heat Indicators")+
ylab("Odds Risk Ratio")+
ggtitle("Comparison of odds risk ratios for different countries
        and indicators of heat exposure")

```

p1

```

#####
#####
# OCTOBER 2023
# D2.3 Preprocessing assigning exposures an selecting the model
# Michalis Koureas (UTH)
#####
#####

rm(list=ls())
#Load packages, clean environment& set working directory
pacman::p_load(dplyr,magrittr,data.table)
library(tidyverse)
library(survival)
library(sjPlot)
library(dlnm)
library(tibble)
library(forestplot)
library(stringr)
library(AICcmoavg)

setwd( ...../data/ANALYSIS/")

#load data

birth_data <- read_csv("..../OUTCOME DATA/birth_data.csv")

# restrict data to cases
cases_data<- birth_data[which(birth_data$preterm == 1), ]
# order by date
cases_data <- cases_data[order(cases_data$date), ]

# ADD CONTROL ROWS FOR EACH CASE - same dow in same month and year
# create dataframe of all dates
alldates <- data.frame(date=seq(as.Date("1999-01-01"),
                               as.Date("2021-12-31"),
                               by='days'))

# add year, month and dow
alldates %<>% mutate(year = lubridate::year(date),
                   month = lubridate::month(date),
                   dow = as.factor(weekdays(date)))

# convert to data table
setDT(alldates)

# convert outcome data to table
cases_data_dt <- setDT(cases_data)

```

```

#insert rows
cases_data_dt1 <- alldates[cases_data_dt[, .(AA,
Year,Day,gweeks,urban,bw_code,delv,mothage,nation_code,family_st,
country,number_born,date,COMMUNE_NAME2,COMMUNE_FID,

NUTS_CODE_3,NUTS_CODE_2,NUTS_CODE_1,KALCODE,preterm=0L, year, month,
dow)],          # outcomes=0 in new rows
                on=.(year, month, dow), allow.cartesian=TRUE][
                cases_data_dt, on=.(AA, date=date), preterm :=
i.preterm]

cases_data1 <- as.data.frame(cases_data_dt1)#convert to dataframe
df <- subset(cases_data1, select = -c(Year, i.date))

#clean environment
rm(list = setdiff(ls(), "df"))

# assign exposures

Meantemp <- read_csv("EXPOSURE DATA/Meantemp.csv")# get mean
temperature data

# Define the number of lookback days
num_previous_days <- 7

# Create a list to store the merged dataframes
merged_data_list <- list()

# Loop through each day offset
for (offset in 1:num_previous_days) { # Start from 0 for the day
before date
  # Create a new column with date - offset days
  df <- df %>%
    mutate(date_minus_offset = date  lubridate::days(offset))

  # Merge the two dataframes based on date_minus_offset and KALCODE
  merged_data <- merge(df, Meantemp, by.x = c("date_minus_offset",
"KALCODE"), by.y = c("Date", "KALCODE"), all.x = TRUE)

  # Rename the Temperature column in the merged dataframe (optional)
  colnames(merged_data)[colnames(merged_data) == "Temperature"] <-
paste("Temperature", offset, sep = "_")

  # Store the merged dataframe in the list
  merged_data_list[[offset]] <- merged_data
}

# extract the first 23 common columns from the first data frame
common_cols <- merged_data_list[[1]][, 1:23]

# Combine the common columns with all data frames

```

```

merged_data <- cbind(common_cols, do.call(cbind,
lapply(merged_data_list, function(df) df[, 24:ncol(df)])))

# Extract the column names
col_names <- colnames(merged_data)

# Check the number of columns
num_columns <- length(col_names)

# Define the new column names
new_col_names <- c(col_names[1:(num_columns - 7)],
"Meantemp0", "Meantemp1", "Meantemp2", "Meantemp3", "Meantemp4",
"Meantemp5", "Meantemp6")

# Rename the columns
colnames(merged_data) <- new_col_names

X1<- merged_data

#procces is repeated for each exposure variable and data are stored as
X1,X2,X3 etc

rm(list = setdiff(ls(), c("X1","X2","X3","X4","X5", "X6","df")))

XALL <- cbind(X1, X2[-c(1:23)], X3[-c(1:23)], X4[-c(1:23)], X5[-
c(1:23)], X6[-c(1:23)])
write.csv(XALL, file = "OUTCOME DATA/ALL_FOR_CC_PRETERM.csv", row.names
= FALSE)

# model selction
#temperature mean
TEMP_MEAN <- df[, grep("Meantemp", names(df))]# get lagged temperature
data

#create cross basis items
CB_POLY_2 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("poly",
degree = 2), arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept =
FALSE))
CB_POLY_3 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("poly",
degree = 3), arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept =
FALSE))
CB_POLY_4 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("poly",
degree = 4), arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept =
FALSE))
CB_BS_3 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("bs", df = 3),
arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_BS_4 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("bs", df = 4),
arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_BS_5 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("bs", df = 5),
arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_BS_6 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("bs", df = 6),
arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))

```

```

CB_BS_7 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("bs", df = 7),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_BS_8 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("bs", df = 8),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_BS_9 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("bs", df = 9),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_BS_10 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("bs", df =
  10), arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_NS_2 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df = 2),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_NS_3 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df = 3),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_NS_4 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df = 4),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_NS_5 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df = 5),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_NS_6 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df = 6),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_NS_7 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df = 7),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_NS_8 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df = 8),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_NS_9 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df = 9),
  arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))
CB_NS_10 <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df =
  10), arglag = list(fun = "poly", degree = 2, intercept = FALSE))

CB_NS_2_NSLAG <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df
  = 2), arglag = list(fun = "ns", knots=logknots(6, 1), int=T))
CB_NS_3_NSLAG <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df
  = 3), arglag = list(fun = "ns", knots=logknots(6, 1), int=T))
CB_NS_4_NSLAG <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df
  = 4), arglag = list(fun = "ns", knots=logknots(6, 1), int=T))
CB_NS_5_NSLAG <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns", df
  = 5), arglag = list(fun = "ns", knots=logknots(6, 1), int=T))

options(na.action="na.exclude")

percentiles <- quantile(TEMP_MEAN$Meantemp0, c(0.25, 0.50, 0.75), na.rm
  = T)

P90<-quantile(TEMP_MEAN$Meantemp0,0.90, na.rm = T)
P10<-quantile(TEMP_MEAN$Meantemp0,0.10, na.rm = T)

CB_NS_2_NSLAG_KNOT <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6,
  argvar = list("ns",
  knots=c(P10,P90)),
  arglag = list(fun = "ns",
  knots=logknots(6, 1),int=T))

CB_NS_3_NSLAG_var <- crossbasis(TEMP_MEAN, lag = 6, argvar = list("ns",
  df=3 ), arglag = list(fun = "ns", knots=logknots(6, 2), int=T))

#fitting conditional logistic regression models (clogit) for each
combination of the crossbasis objects

```

```

MODEL_POLY_2<- clogit(preterm~CB_POLY_2+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_POLY_3<- clogit(preterm~CB_POLY_3+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_POLY_4<- clogit(preterm~CB_POLY_4+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_BS_3<- clogit(preterm~CB_BS_3+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_BS_4<- clogit(preterm~CB_BS_4+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_BS_5<- clogit(preterm~CB_BS_5+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_BS_6<- clogit(preterm~CB_BS_6+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_BS_7<- clogit(preterm~CB_BS_7+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_BS_8<- clogit(preterm~CB_BS_8+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_BS_9<- clogit(preterm~CB_BS_9+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_BS_10<- clogit(preterm~CB_BS_10+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_2<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_2+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_3<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_3+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_4<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_4+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_5<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_5+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_6<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_6+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_7<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_7+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_8<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_8+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_9<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_9+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_10<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_10+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_2_NSLAG<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_2_NSLAG+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_3_NSLAG<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_3_NSLAG+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_4_NSLAG<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_4_NSLAG+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_5_NSLAG<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_5_NSLAG+strata(AA), df)
MODEL_NS_2_NSLAG_KNOT<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_2_NSLAG_KNOT+strata(AA),
df)
MODEL_NS_3_NSLAG_var<- clogit(preterm~CB_NS_3_NSLAG_var+strata(AA), df)

```

```
#get predictions
```

```

P_POLY_2 <- crosspred(CB_POLY_2, MODEL_POLY_2)
P_POLY_3 <- crosspred(CB_POLY_3, MODEL_POLY_3)
P_POLY_4 <- crosspred(CB_POLY_4, MODEL_POLY_4)
P_BS_3 <- crosspred(CB_BS_3, MODEL_BS_3)
P_BS_4 <- crosspred(CB_BS_4, MODEL_BS_4)
P_BS_5 <- crosspred(CB_BS_5, MODEL_BS_5)
P_BS_6 <- crosspred(CB_BS_6, MODEL_BS_6)
P_BS_7 <- crosspred(CB_BS_7, MODEL_BS_7)
P_BS_8 <- crosspred(CB_BS_8, MODEL_BS_8)
P_BS_9 <- crosspred(CB_BS_9, MODEL_BS_9)
P_BS_10 <- crosspred(CB_BS_10, MODEL_BS_10)
P_NS_2 <- crosspred(CB_NS_2, MODEL_NS_2)
P_NS_3 <- crosspred(CB_NS_3, MODEL_NS_3)
P_NS_4 <- crosspred(CB_NS_4, MODEL_NS_4)
P_NS_5 <- crosspred(CB_NS_5, MODEL_NS_5)
P_NS_6 <- crosspred(CB_NS_6, MODEL_NS_6)
P_NS_7 <- crosspred(CB_NS_7, MODEL_NS_7)
P_NS_8 <- crosspred(CB_NS_8, MODEL_NS_8)
P_NS_9 <- crosspred(CB_NS_9, MODEL_NS_9)
P_NS_10 <- crosspred(CB_NS_10, MODEL_NS_10)

```

```

P_NS_2_NSLAG<- crosspred(CB_NS_2_NSLAG, MODEL_NS_2_NSLAG)
P_NS_3_NSLAG<- crosspred(CB_NS_3_NSLAG, MODEL_NS_3_NSLAG)
P_NS_4_NSLAG<- crosspred(CB_NS_4_NSLAG, MODEL_NS_4_NSLAG)
P_NS_5_NSLAG<- crosspred(CB_NS_5_NSLAG, MODEL_NS_5_NSLAG)

```

```

P_NS_2_NSLAG_KNOT<- crosspred(CB_NS_2_NSLAG_KNOT,
MODEL_NS_2_NSLAG_KNOT)
P_NS_3_NSLAG_var<- crosspred(CB_NS_3_NSLAG_var, MODEL_NS_3_NSLAG_var)

#plot
# Create a list of prediction objects
prediction_list <- list(P_POLY_2, P_POLY_3, P_POLY_4, P_BS_3, P_BS_4,
P_BS_5,
                        P_BS_6, P_BS_7, P_BS_8, P_BS_9, P_BS_10,
                        P_NS_2, P_NS_3, P_NS_4, P_NS_5, P_NS_6,
                        P_NS_7, P_NS_8, P_NS_9,
P_NS_10,P_NS_2_NSLAG,P_NS_3_NSLAG,
P_NS_5_NSLAG,P_NS_5_NSLAG,P_NS_2_NSLAG_KNOT,P_NS_3_NSLAG_var
)

models <- list(MODEL_POLY_2,MODEL_POLY_3,MODEL_POLY_4,
              MODEL_BS_3,
              MODEL_BS_4,
              MODEL_BS_5,
              MODEL_BS_6,
              MODEL_BS_7,
              MODEL_BS_8,
              MODEL_BS_9,
              MODEL_BS_10,
              MODEL_NS_2,
              MODEL_NS_3,
              MODEL_NS_4,
              MODEL_NS_5,
              MODEL_NS_6,
              MODEL_NS_7,
              MODEL_NS_8,
              MODEL_NS_9,
              MODEL_NS_10,
              MODEL_NS_2_NSLAG,MODEL_NS_3_NSLAG,MODEL_NS_4_NSLAG,
              MODEL_NS_5_NSLAG, MODEL_NS_2_NSLAG_KNOT,
              MODEL_NS_3_NSLAG_var)
mod.names <- c(
  "MODEL_POLY_2",
  "MODEL_POLY_3",
  "MODEL_POLY_4",
  "MODEL_BS_3",
  "MODEL_BS_4",
  "MODEL_BS_5",
  "MODEL_BS_6",
  "MODEL_BS_7",
  "MODEL_BS_8",
  "MODEL_BS_9",
  "MODEL_BS_10",
  "MODEL_NS_2",
  "MODEL_NS_3",
  "MODEL_NS_4",
  "MODEL_NS_5",
  "MODEL_NS_6",
  "MODEL_NS_7",

```

```

"MODEL_NS_8",
"MODEL_NS_9",
"MODEL_NS_10",
"MODEL_NS_2_NSLAG",
"MODEL_NS_3_NSLAG",
"MODEL_NS_4_NSLAG",
"MODEL_NS_5_NSLAG",
"MODEL_NS_2_NSLAG_KNOT",
"MODEL_NS_3_NSLAG_var"
)

aictab(cand.set = models, modnames = mod.names)

#calculate AIC of each model
aictab(cand.set = models, modnames = mod.names)

# Create an empty plot to serve as the base for adding plots
plot(1, type="n", ylab="OR overall", xlab="Temperature °C", ylim=c(0.9,
1.5), xlim=c(-3, 32), main="Temperature vs Preterm birth")

# Loop through the prediction objects and add them to the plot
for (pred in prediction_list) {
  lines(pred, "overall", col=rainbow(length(prediction_list)))
}

# Add a title to the plot
title("Temperature vs Preterm birth")
mtext("Overall effect (26 model modifications)", side = 3, line = 0,
cex = 1.1)

#calculate AIC for each model
AIC_values<-AIC(MODEL_POLY_2,MODEL_POLY_3,MODEL_POLY_4,
MODEL_BS_3,
MODEL_BS_4,
MODEL_BS_5,
MODEL_BS_6,
MODEL_BS_7,
MODEL_BS_8,
MODEL_BS_9,
MODEL_BS_10,
MODEL_NS_2,
MODEL_NS_3,
MODEL_NS_4,
MODEL_NS_5,
MODEL_NS_6,
MODEL_NS_7,
MODEL_NS_8,
MODEL_NS_9,
MODEL_NS_10)

# Find the index of the model with the lowest AIC
index_lowest_AIC <- which.min(AIC_values$AIC)

```

9.3 Appendix C: Heat metrics acquisition and preparatory analysis for Greece

The Copernicus Climate Change Service includes in its products the ERA5-Land dataset^[1] produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) that contains the land component of the ERA5 climate reanalysis^[2] variables with an improved resolution in a grid of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$. Data are available in the Climate Data Store (CDS).

The ERA5-Land dataset has been selected for analysis involving the Greek Communes considering its improved spatial scale compared to ERA5. Specifically for Greece (Figures 24 and 25), ERA5-Land tiles have a higher spatial resolution of $\sim 10 \times 10$ km (95 sqkm average area per tile) compared to ERA5's $\sim 25 \times 25$ km (604 sqkm average area per tile).

Figure 24: ERA5 tiles, ERA5 bounding box used for Greece and Greek Communes administrative boundaries are visible. ERA5 data tiles are coloured based on the daily mean temperatures of 1-1-2020

Figure 25: ERA5-Land tiles, ERA5-Land bounding box used for Greece and Greek Communes administrative boundaries are visible. ERA5-Land data tiles are coloured based on the daily mean temperatures of 1-1-2020

Figure 26: Graph showing the average area that data tiles and Greek communes are occupying

Since Greek communes are on average 405 sqkm, the ERA5-Land's resolution aligns better with the size of the communes offering on average 4 measurements per commune (Figure 26). This allows for analysis that is more area-specific and can account for microclimates and small-scale geographic features that might affect local variability in weather patterns or extremes. To achieve this, calculations of heat metrics for Greece were carried out on an hourly temporal scale for a bounding box using a methodology described in “A high-spatial-resolution dataset of human thermal stress indices over South and East Asia” by Yechao Yan et. al.^[3] The authors share freely available python scripts that allow users to calculate heat metrics for any part of the world^[4]. The first step is to download both ERA5 and ERA5-Land datasets by using CDS API.

This is due to the fact, that one variable not available in ERA5-Land but necessary to calculate MRT and other heat metrics is fdir, which represents the direct solar radiation at the surface level. This variable is exclusively accessible within the ERA5 dataset, so the fdir data is transformed from a spatial scale of 0.25° by 0.25° to a finer scale of 0.1° by 0.1° to match the spatial resolution of the other ERA5-Land derived variables. This rescaling is achieved through the application of the nearest-neighbour interpolation method, conserving the original data values during the regriding process.

Table 7: Derived indices calculated over Greece using the methods described by Yechao Yan et. all

Derived Thermal Indices	Full Name of the Indices	Calculated Variables
AT	Apparent Temperature	Daily mean
HI	Heat Index	Daily mean
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index	Daily mean
WBGT	Wet-bulb Globe Temperature	Daily mean

After calculating AT, HI, UTCI, WBGT on an hourly basis, summary statistics calculating daily means were applied and saved to NetCDF format (.nc)^[5] for the next step of the geospatial aggregation analysis.

Geospatial boundary data for Greek communes were downloaded in the shapefile (.shp) format from the Geographical Information System of the Commission (GISCO) [\[6\]](#), which is a repository managed by Eurostat containing diverse geospatial data.

To assign daily means of the derived thermal indices from ERA5-Land tiles over the Greek communes, we used a built in QGIS function (native:zonalstatisticsfb[\[7\]](#)) provided by QGIS[\[8\]](#) (native c++), that calculates statistics of a raster layer (.nc) for each feature of an overlapping polygon vector layer. The zonal 'mean' value is weighted based on % of zone area that occupy a raster pixel(s).

For our case, a modified custom python script that utilized the QGIS function calculated mean zonal statistics provided a .nc file that every band represents a date measurement of ERA5-Land derived indices, and the Greek commune's shapefile. The resultant zonal statistics were systematically exported to individual comma-separated values (.csv) files daily. Subsequently, an additional Python script was employed to consolidate these outputs into an aggregated dataset. This compiled dataset encompasses daily values spanning from January 1, 1998, to December 31, 2022, with the total data storage requirement for each indicator approximating 48 megabytes.

References:

- [\[1\]](#) Muñoz Sabater, J. (2019): ERA5-Land hourly data from 1950 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). DOI: 10.24381/cds.e2161bac (Accessed on 01-11-2023)
- [\[2\]](#) Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Rozum, I., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Dee, D., Thépaut, J-N. (2023): ERA5 hourly data on pressure levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), DOI: 10.24381/cds.bd0915c6 (Accessed on 01-11-2023)
- [\[3\]](#) Yan, Yechao, Yangyang Xu, and Shuping Yue. "A high-spatial-resolution dataset of human thermal stress indices over South and East Asia." *Scientific Data* 8, no. 1 (2021): 1-14.

[4] Yan, Yechao; Xu, Yangyang; Yue, Shuping (2021): A High-spatial-resolution Dataset of Human Thermal Stress Indices over South and East Asia. figshare. Collection. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.5196296>

[5] The .nc file extension or the Network Common Data Form (NetCDF), is used for the storage and sharing of array-oriented scientific data, especially in the fields of atmospheric and oceanic research.

[6] GISCO – Eurostat: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/administrative-units-statistical-units/communes>

[7]

https://github.com/JanCaha/r_package_qgis/blob/HEAD/R/qgis_zonalstatisticsfb.R

[8] QGIS is an open-source Geographic Information System (GIS) used for creating, editing, and analyzing spatial data, and is maintained by the Open Source Geospatial Foundation.